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Analysis of future residual loads in Germany for 2030-2050 and possible accuracy gains of their modelling

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Preface

This thesis was written at the concluding stage of my master's degree programme in business administration with a focus on sustainability management in cooperation with the Institute of Infrastructure and Resource Management at the University of Leipzig.

I would like to thank Philipp Lerch in particular, who supported me as my supervisor with valuable tips during the preparation of my thesis. His always friendly and constructive manner as well as his expertise and willingness to help at any time made a decisive contribution to the success of this thesis. I would also like to thank Peter Pfeiderer, who was a valuable discussion partner and was able to provide helpful tips in the course of this thesis thanks to his programming expertise.

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Abstract

The future German energy system will focus heavily on renewable energies in order to comply with the ambitious climate protection targets. A key challenge of this energy transition is ensuring a reliable coverage of residual load through renewable energy sources.

This thesis addresses two research questions. Firstly, it is examined how the residual load will evolve in the future and derives implications for the design of the future energy system. Secondly, it will be investigated if significant accuracy gains can be achieved in the modelling of the future residual load.

To answer this, a simulation model was developed to estimate the future electricity generation from PV and wind power, taking into account three different scenarios. This generation is offset against the electricity load to calculate the residual load at an hourly resolution. The model was implemented in Python, with supplementary analyses conducted in Excel. The spatial granularity distinguishes between an aggregated national level and a federal state specific level. The renewable capacity data were sourced from the Marktstammdatenregister. The different scenarios are compared with respect to their results as well as modelling accuracy.

The analysis reveals a significant increase in negative residual load in the future, while variations in positive residual load remain comparatively smaller. This is due to a significant temporal mismatch between high renewable electricity generation and high electricity demand. These findings highlight the urgent need for advanced flexibility options, such as energy storage, demand-side management, and sector coupling, to ensure a stable renewable-based energy supply. Furthermore, the results indicate that higher spatial granularity and the consideration of future technological advancements can improve the modelling accuracy.

Future research should focus on optimizing the design and implementation of flexibility options. The proposed model provides a solid foundation for further refinements and scenario-based evaluations.

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List of abbreviations

RL	Residual load
PV	Photovoltaic
MaStR	Marktstammdatenregister (Market data register)
PVGIS	Photovoltaic Geographical Information System of the European Commission
EEG	Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (Renewable Energy Act)
Wp/kWp	Watt peak/kilowatt peak
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
ENTSO-G	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Gas
TYNDP	Ten year net development plan
W/kW/MW/GW	Watt/Kilowatt/Megawatt/Gigawatt
GWh	Gigawatt hours

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and thesis structure

The Climate Crisis represents one of the most substantial challenges that humanity has to face. While this constitutes an enormous task, the impacts associated with the Climate Crisis are increasingly severe and occur more frequently. The causative increase of greenhouse gas emissions necessitates the transition to a renewable energy system as one of the most prominent emission sources. Therefore, an extensive emission reduction is needed in order to drive down the rapid rise of the global mean temperature of Earth. While the expansion of renewable energy sources is an effective means to reach this target, it poses entirely new challenges. One of the most crucial aspects is the intermittent supply of electricity from renewable sources, such as solar and wind energy, which is caused by fluctuating weather conditions. Thus, the question of the coverage of residual load (RL), that cannot be supplied with renewable electricity, is raised. This question is crucial for the future energy system and plays a deciding role in the challenge of combining sustainable energy sources with security of supply at all times.

In the current scientific as well as societal dialogue, this question is discussed very intensively. As the expansion of renewable energy made significant progresses so far, events of both highly positive as well as highly negative RL will play a decisive role in the future energy system.¹ As of current state, it is not conclusively answered, how severe those events will be in the future and which possibilities will be used to deal with them. To contribute to this question, this thesis aims at describing the future RL more detailedly. Furthermore, it will be examined, if the modelling accuracy of the future RL can be enhanced and which assumptions and steps are necessary to do so. Consequently, a simulation model will be introduced, and various scenarios will be calculated to gain insights into the issues raised. The main data sources are represented by capacity data of the Marktstammdatenregister (MaStR) as well as weather data on solar radiation and wind speeds. This data is used to estimate the future renewable generation that is offset by the electricity consumption in the following to calculate the RL.

The following thesis is divided into four parts. Firstly, the theoretical background on renewable energy systems and the term RL is introduced. Thereafter, the methodology of the thesis is explained, which was applied to answer the research questions. In the third part, the results of the RL analysis are presented and evaluated. Finally, the implications of the research are drawn, and a conclusion is presented.

¹ (Korb 06.01.2025)

1.2 Research questions

As already mentioned in chapter 1.1, the following research questions should be answered by this thesis:

1. How will the future RL in Germany develop and which implications do those developments have for the future energy system?
2. Are there significant accuracy gains to be achieved in the modelling of the future residual load in Germany in consideration of higher spatial granularity and assumptions on future technology development?

1.3 Literature review

There already have been significant efforts to model the German energy system, aiming at researching different aspects of its future development. One crucial focus is the examination of the coverage of the electricity load with renewable sources and the associated RL. In Table 1, the most relevant scientific advancements regarding the presented topic will be introduced shortly. In the following, the relevance of the current thesis is derived.

While there are a quite substantial number of theses that dealt with the modelling of the future renewable generation, fewer theses focussed on the modelling of the RL. This might be reasoned by the fact that the modelling of the future electricity load further increases the complexity and reliability of the projection. However, a detailed consideration of the future RL, as proposed in this thesis, delivers significant insights into a meaningful design of the future energy system. While there are studies, such as the Kopernikus-Project Ariadne², that follow similar goals as this thesis, there exist also papers with a very similar methodology. Especially the elaboration from Lehneis et al.³ uses a similar approach to estimate the future renewable generation. However, this thesis extends their consideration by taking into account the development of the specific generation profile of Photovoltaic (PV) plants in the future. Therefore, it represents a further advancement since the development of the orientation and tilt angles are considered very sophisticated rather than just set fixed to a certain orientation and tilt

² (Jürgens et al. 2024)

³ (Lehneis et al. 2022)

angle. Apart from that, there are also various publications that point out significant periods of positive and negative RL in the future, that are heavily influenced by daily and seasonal variations. Noticeably, every considered research paper uses an hourly resolution in the modelling, most likely due to the hourly resolution of available weather data.

Table 1: Literature review of most relevant research papers

Ref. year & first author	Title	Spatial / Temporal resolution	Objective	Method	Results
2024, Jürgens (Kopernikus-Projekt Ariadne)	Flexibilität im deutschen Energiesystem bis 2045: Beitrag verschiedener Technologien auf dem Weg zur Klimaneutralität	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National (Germany) • Hourly resolution 	Analysis of increasing flexibility needs in the German energy system and how different technologies can adapt their operations over time to achieve climate neutrality by 2045	Utilization of REMod energy system model to conduct an intersectoral flexibility analysis up to 2045	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High positive RL hours in morning and evening hours in winter, high negative RL hours in midday hours in summer • Significant flexibility potentials can be provided by batteries, electricity imports/exports, load management, electrolysis and flexible backup gas turbines
2022, Lehneis	Spatiotemporal Modelling of the Electricity Production from Variable Renewable Energies in Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National (Germany) • Hourly resolution 	Develop a model to simulate electricity production from fluctuating renewable energies in Germany with high spatial and temporal resolution	Creation of a spatiotemporal model that integrates geospatial data and time series of weather conditions to estimate fluctuating renewable electricity production using power curves	The model provides detailed insights into the variability of renewable energy production across different regions and times, aiding in the planning and integration of fluctuating renewable energies into the energy system
2024, Grochowicz	Using Power System Modelling Outputs to Identify Weather-Induced Extreme Events in Highly Renewable Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europe • Hourly resolution 	Identify extreme events in power systems with high renewable energy penetration that are induced by weather conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of PyPSA-Eur capacity expansion model with 40 years of ERA5 reanalysis data • Analysis of shadow prices to identify system-defining events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of weather patterns leading to power system stress • Traditional meteorological approaches fail to capture all system-defining events due to complex interactions of transmission and storage
2022, Kockel	Does renewable electricity supply match with energy demand? – A spatio-temporal analysis for the German case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NUTS-3 level (districts) in Germany • Hourly resolution 	Analysis of match between renewable energy supply and demand in time and space, and assess impacts of sector coupling on infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combined top-down and bottom-up analysis • Consumer-driven approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant regional and temporal mismatches between renewable supply and demand • Sector coupling increases electricity demand and changes load profiles; different RES placement strategies have varying impacts on grid requirements

2022, Schindler	Importance of renewable resource variability for electricity mix transformation: A case study from Germany based on electricity market data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National (Germany) • Hourly resolution (2015 to 2021) 	Analysis of the development and potential of renewable energy shares in the German electricity mix and discuss future challenges for implementing the transformation until 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of actual electricity generation and consumption data • High-resolution wavelet analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant mismatches between renewable supply and demand • Natural variability of solar and wind identified as main challenge • Achievement of 2030 targets requires strict compliance with expansion goals and moderate increase in electricity consumption
Current thesis for reference		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NUTS-1 level (federal states) in Germany • Hourly resolution 	Analysis of composition of future RL in Germany and examination of significant modelling accuracy gains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of simulation model for PV and wind generation using power curves of capacity factors and weather data • Consideration of refined assumptions on future technology development (1. PV generation profile based on orientation/tilt angle and 2. Wind speed adjustment on future hub height) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing relevance of pos. and neg. RL events in the future • Mitigating effect of alternative PV profile and wind speed modelling on pos./neg. RL • Achievable accuracy gains of modelling by taking into account higher spatial resolution and refined technology assumptions

Source: own illustration based on considered research papers

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Renewable energy systems

Renewable energy systems are a crucial key to achieve a successful energy transition. The considered technologies in the course of this thesis are PV and wind energy. This is due to the calculation of the RL that was conducted in this thesis and will be explained in the next subchapter. As the precise technical process of the generation of electricity by PV and wind power is not relevant to this thesis, it will not be considered in detail.⁴ Instead, the focus lies on the influence factors on the electricity generation that will be further analysed in the following chapters. For the PV systems, especially the capacity as well as the orientation and tilt angle are important characteristics that determine their electricity generation. The different materials or PV technologies that can be used for the PV systems are not viewed in more detail. For wind turbines, the capacity as well as the hub height and the rotor diameter represent the main indicators of their size/performance.

The capacity of PV systems is specified in Watt peak (Wp) and reflects the maximum electrical output that can be provided by the modules. The indication of the Wp makes the comparison of different types PV systems/modules possible as it takes into account conditions such as the outside temperature and light irradiation.⁵ The capacity in Wp corresponds to the so called “Bruttoleistung” (gross capacity) that is used to specify the characteristics of PV systems in the MaStR. As the gross capacity is the most meaningful characteristic for the capacity of a PV system, it was used for the analysis. Apart from that, the “Nettoleistung” (net capacity) is also specified. It includes the capacity of the corresponding inverter that converts the direct current of the PV systems in alternating current that can be distributed by the electric grid. The net capacity uses the respectively lower value of the PV system and the inverter.

The orientation and tilt angles of PV systems have a considerable effect on their total electricity generation as well as the daily and seasonal profile of this generation. This is justified by the fact that PV modules perform best when they are aligned orthogonally to the sun. As the sun is not stationary over the day and shows seasonal variations, there is no optimal alignment of PV systems at all times, except for two-axis tracked systems that follow the course of the sun. The orientation angle is specified by the azimuth, which is defined as the horizontal angle of a given location compared to a fixed point. While there may exist various conventions about what is used as the fixed point, in this thesis

⁴ Further information on the operation principles of [PV](#) and [wind power](#)

⁵ (TRITEC 23.06.2021)

the azimuth is oriented on the southern sky direction. This means that the azimuth of 0° represents ideal south orientation of PV systems. Analogously, 90° represent ideal west orientation and -90° represent ideal east orientation. The ideal north orientation takes the two values of ±180°. The tilt angle only alternates between 0° and 90°. A value of 90° represents vertically installed PV systems whereas 0° represent PV systems that are laid out horizontally. The influence of the orientation and tilt angle on the relative yield of PV systems for an exemplary location is displayed in table 2. However, it has to be noted that this only refers to the total yield and does not take into account the respective generation profiles. This is due to the course of the sun that rises in the east and goes down in the west. This leads to a higher generation of east-oriented PV systems in the morning and a higher generation of west-oriented PV systems in the evening. The implications of this effect on the PV generation profile is further discussed in chapters 3.5 and 4.4.

Table 2: Exemplary relative PV yield in Freiburg, Germany

		Tilt angle									
		0°	10°	20°	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°	90°
Orientation angle	-90° (east)	84%	83%	82%	81%	78%	74%	70%	64%	57%	50%
	-45°	84%	89%	92%	94%	94%	92%	88%	83%	75%	66%
	0° (south)	84%	91%	96%	99%	100%	99%	95%	89%	81%	71%
	45°	84%	89%	92%	93%	93%	91%	87%	81%	73%	64%
	90° (west)	84%	83%	81%	79%	76%	72%	68%	62%	55%	48%
	135°	84%	77%	70%	63%	56%	50%	45%	39%	33%	28%
	180° (north)	84%	75%	65%	56%	47%	39%	31%	26%	21%	17%

Source: own illustration based on calculations from Wirth 2024⁶

The capacity (or “nominal/rated capacity”) of wind turbines is specified in Watt (W) and reflects the maximum electrical output that can be provided given optimal wind conditions, mostly between 12-16 m/s. To describe the power that can be supplied during the respective wind speed, so called power curves are used. Characteristic to wind turbines is also the existence of a cut-in speed as well as a cut-out speed. The cut-in speed signals the minimum wind speed at which the turbine is able to generate electricity and lies typically between 3-4 m/s. If the wind reaches the cut-out speed of the wind turbine, it stops operating to prevent damages to the rotor. This point is typically reached

⁶ (Wirth 2024)

at a speed of 25 m/s.⁷ Contrary to PV systems, wind turbines only have one definition of capacity which is why the gross capacity is set equal to the net capacity in the MaStR.

The two most apparent characteristics of wind turbines are the hub height as well as the rotor diameter. Although there are complex relations between the rotor diameter⁸ and the corresponding generation of wind turbines, in this analysis the main influence is described by the hub height. This is because the hub height marks the height of the installed rotor and is decisive for the wind speeds that can be harvested. Therefore, in this analysis, the hub height was used to examine the influence of the future technological development of wind turbines on the harvestable wind speeds. This will be explained in more detail in 3.6 and the results will be presented in 4.5.

2.2 Residual load

The RL is a widely used concept in Energy Economics. It describes the electrical load that remains after deducting the feed-in of fluctuating renewable energies (PV and wind). Therefore, it also quantifies the electrical load that needs to be covered by (mostly) non-renewable, steerable sources, such as Gas, Coal, and Oil. However, the RL can also be covered by renewable alternatives, such as flexible Biomass plants or pump water storages. Another possible source could be nuclear power which can be characterised as non-renewable but decarbonised.

The RL can be exactly zero but will take on a positive or negative value most of the time. A positive RL implies that the current electrical load cannot be fully covered by fluctuating renewable energies and additional generation sources are required. Conversely, negative RL occurs whenever the generation by PV and wind exceeds the electrical load. In turn, the overproducing assets either need to be shut down or additional load will need to be switched on in order to not harm the electrical grid and to guarantee a stable frequency. In the course of 2024, there were noticeably more times of positive RL than negative RL.⁹ An exact balance of the electrical load and the generation by fluctuating renewable sources, which would result in a RL of zero, practically never appears. However, in a completely decarbonised energy system, the resulting positive RL would need to be covered by renewable sources, such as Biomass, pump water storages, or the provision of flexibility to the system. Negative RL hours could also play an important

⁷ For more information on wind power curves see wind-turbine-models.com

⁸ For more information on the rotor diameter and its influence see igwindkraft.at

⁹ (Burger 21.10.2024)

role in this future system because they enable the possibility to store excess electricity (for example by battery electric storages and Power to Gas) and use it in times of scarcity. Therefore, both positive and negative RL deliver a crucial incentive to flexibilise the future electricity supply to its changing composition and requirements.

3 Method

3.1 Overall methodology

The following analysis that represents the main part of the present thesis is described in the following. It is explained which methodological steps were applied in the underlying analysis and how those steps are complemented by the subsequent analysis. This results in a subdivision in three generation scenarios that correspond to those steps. The scopes of the different scenarios are listed in table 3. While the underlying scenario uses aggregated weather data and capacity timeseries to estimate the generation, the advanced scenarios use federal state specific data as well as more precise assumptions. Figure 1 depicts the general methodology of the analysis. The main idea of the analysis as well as basic aspects of the underlying analysis (scenario “DE_Base_20xx”) and possible enhancements of it (further scenarios) were formulated by Philipp Lerch and Peter Pfeleiderer of the University of Leipzig. On the basis of this, the further scenarios were developed in this thesis as well as their comparison and implications. In the following chapters, precise explanations of the detailed modelling steps are given. Finally, the main data sources are listed, connected to the steps that they were used in.

Table 3: Overview of scenario scopes

Scenario	“DE_Base_20xx”	“BL_Base_20xx”	“BL_Tech_20xx”
Aggregated weather data and capacity timeseries	✓	✗	✗
Federal state specific weather data and capacity timeseries	✗	✓	✓
Refined assumptions on wind speeds and PV generation profile	✗	✗	✓

Source: own illustration

The frame and boxes highlighted in blue describe the underlying analysis (see figure 1). In a first step, the facility data of the MaStR¹⁰ was used to construct a timeseries of the

¹⁰ (Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation, Post und Eisenbahnen 2024)

daily capacity expansion. Secondly, the hourly generation was divided by the installed capacity in the corresponding timestep to calculate the historic capacity factors. In order to model the future generation, the historic capacity factors were applied to the future capacity expansion pathways. The future capacity expansion pathways were assumed based on the historic capacity expansion as well as the statutory expansion targets. Finally, the resulting future generation was offset with the electricity consumption to calculate the future RL. The underlying analysis is described by the scenario “DE_Base_20xx”.¹¹

The frame and boxes highlighted in orange/red describe the subsequent analyses. Within these advanced analyses, the facility data was further processed and analysed. This resulted in a more detailed analysis of the capacity per federal state and in turn more spatially granular capacity expansion timeseries. Apart from that, the facilities were also evaluated with respect to their characteristics, such as the orientation/tilt angle for PV and the hub height for wind turbines. This acted as the basis for refined assumptions that take into account the specific technology development. The insights of this step were put together with the historic capacity factors as well as the assumed future capacity expansion pathways to model a refined future generation. The data for this was taken from the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System of the European Commission (PVGIS) to construct the PV generation profiles and from the Regional statistics to model the future wind speeds. In a final step, the resulting alternative future generation was offset with the electricity consumption again to calculate the refined future RL. The subsequent analysis is described by the scenarios “BL_Base_20xx” and “BL_Tech_20xx”.

The main approach that was chosen is the formulation of a simulation model. Regarding the tools to analyse the data, Python and Excel were used. Table 4 lists the different segments of the code with respect to their input and output data. The (main) data source is the MaStR in order to obtain the facility data. The considered technologies are PV, wind onshore and wind offshore. The spatial scope is Germany (on NUTS-1 level), and the temporal granularity is hourly.

In the following, precise methodological explanations of the main steps will be given.

¹¹ „xx” acts as a place holder for the considered key year and can take on the values 30, 40, or 50 for 2030, 2040, or 2050

Figure 1: Methodology scheme

Source: own illustration

Table 4: Code overview

Module	Lines of code	Keyword	Description	Figure/ Table	Pages
pv_analysis	1-45	PV Data import	Import PV data from MaStR	—	14-15
	46-77	PV Data preparation	Prepare dataframe for analysis by excluding and formatting certain values	—	15-16
	78-130	PV temporal distribution	Analysis of capacity distribution over time	Fig. 9, 10	30-31
	131-236	PV Orientation angle	Calculation of capacity per orientation angle	Fig. 11, 43, 44	31-33, 78
	237-327	PV Tilt angle	Calculation of capacity per tilt angle	Fig. 12, 45, 46	33-34, 79
	328-348	Combined orientation/tilt angle	Analysis of relative capacity per combined orientation/tilt angle	Tab. 3	34
	349-423	Normalised PV generation profiles	Construction of normalised PV generation profiles using PVGIS	Fig. 2	18-20
	424-827	Projected future PV generation profiles	Calculation of average PV generation profiles historical and in the future key years	Fig. 3, 27, 28, 29	20-22, 52-55
	828-927	PV location	Calculation of capacity per location	Fig. 13, 47, 48	35-36, 80
	928-963	PV federal state	Calculation of capacity per federal state	Fig. 6	27-28
	964-986	PV federal state future	Calculation of future yearly capacity expansion per federal state	Fig. 54	16-17, 84, 87
	987-1012	Daily installed PV capacity	Calculation of historical daily capacity expansion	—	—
	1013-1036	Daily cumulative PV capacity	Calculation of historical daily cumulative capacity	Fig. 4	26-27
	1037-1062	Yearly installed PV capacity	Calculation of historical yearly capacity expansion	Fig. 5	26-27
	1063-1096	Daily installed PV capacity federal state	Calculation of daily/ monthly capacity expansion per federal state	—	—
	1097-1169	Daily cumulative PV capacity federal state	Calculation of daily/ monthly cumulative capacity per federal state	Fig. 7, 41, 42	29, 77
	1170-1198	PV share federal state	Calculation of share of capacity per federal state over time	Fig. 8	29-30
	1199-1225	PV facility age	Calculation of capacity per facility age	Fig. 49	36, 81

	1226-1248	PV sum test	Tests to examine relevance of excluded values	—	—
	1249-1282	PV spatial distribution	Calculation of capacity per geographical location	Fig. 14	36-37
wind_analysis	1-32	Wind data import	Import wind data from MaStR	—	14-15
	33-73	Wind data preparation	Prepare dataframe for analysis by excluding and formatting certain values	—	15-16
	74-117	Wind temporal distribution	Analysis of capacity distribution over time	Fig. 21, 22	43-44
	118-153	Wind federal state	Calculation of capacity per federal state	Fig. 17	39-40
	154-196	Wind federal state/sea location future	Calculation of future yearly capacity expansion per federal state and sea location	Fig. 55, 56	16-17, 85-86, 88
	197-240	Wind Share sea location	Calculation of share of capacity per sea location over time	Fig. 20	42-43
	241-266	Daily installed wind capacity	Calculation of historical daily capacity expansion	—	—
	267-289	Daily cumulative wind capacity	Calculation of historical daily cumulative capacity	Fig. 15	38
	290-315	Yearly installed wind capacity	Calculation of historical yearly capacity expansion	Fig. 16	38-39
	316-355	Daily installed wind capacity federal state/sea location	Calculation of daily/monthly capacity expansion per federal state and sea location	—	—
	356-439	Daily cumulative wind capacity federal state/sea location	Calculation of daily/monthly cumulative capacity per federal state and sea location	Fig. 18, 50, 51	40-41, 81-82
	440-467	Wind share federal state	Calculation of share of capacity per federal state over time	Fig. 19	41-42
	468-494	Wind facility age	Calculation of capacity per facility age	Fig. 53	47, 83
	495-510	Wind sum test	Tests to examine relevance of excluded values	—	—
	511-593	Wind Rotor diameter	Analysis of rotor diameter distribution over time	Fig. 52	46, 82
	594-697	Wind hub height	Analysis of hub height distribution over time	Fig. 23, 24	45-46
	698-735	Wind spatial distribution	Calculation of capacity per geographical location	Fig. 25	47-48

Residual load	1-112	Historical capacity factors	Import main input data and calculate historical hourly capacity factors	—	17
	113-339	Power curve renewables	Regression of capacity factors on weather data to construct power curves	Fig. 38, 39, 40	17, 75-76
	340-386	Alternative PV profile and wind data	Import of previously calculated future PV profiles and calculation of future wind speeds with higher hub height	—	22-23
	387-566	Function Renewable generation estimation (Germany aggregated)	Function to estimate renewable generation based on power curves, future renewable capacity and weather data (Scenario "DE_Base_xx")	—	17-18, 49-52
	567-809	Function Renewable generation estimation (federal state specific)	Function to estimate renewable generation based on power curves, future renewable capacity and weather data (Scenarios "BL_Base_xx" and "BL_Tech_xx")	—	17-18, 49-52
	810-1088	Renewable generation estimation	Execute functions to calculate renewable generation per scenario	Fig. 26	17-18, 49-52
	1089-1469	RL analysis	Offset renewable generation with consumption data to calculate future RL per scenario	Fig. 30-37, 57-74	23-24, 56-64, 89-102
	1470-1595	Comparison RL timeseries	Calculation of difference between RL scenario timeseries	—	56

Source: own illustration based on incorporated code

3.2 Analysis of current renewable energy systems

In the course of the present thesis, PV systems and wind turbines were thoroughly analysed as they represent the two crucial technologies for the determination of the RL. The data of the facilities was taken from the MaStR that provides system sharp data of the respective technologies and their characteristics. As a comprehensive official registry, it guarantees a good data quality and has a wide range of characteristics that can be analysed. For the purpose of this thesis, the collective facility data was extracted

using the overall data extract function. The last operation start date that was considered in the analysis was the 31.05.2024. The data was analysed using the programming language Python. Apart from various negligible pieces of information, such as identification numbers and further technical specifications, the following characteristics were chosen as potentially insightful:

- For PV systems: operation start date, gross capacity, federal state, postal code, operational status, orientation and tilt angle
- For wind turbines: operation start date, gross capacity, federal state, latitude, longitude, operational status, hub height, rotor diameter and sea location

After reading the XML-files, that store the raw data, the unnecessary columns were deleted in order to ensure conciseness and good performance. Moreover, the facilities that were either temporarily or permanently decommissioned as well as facilities that are just in the planning stage were also excluded. Non available values of the operation start date for both technologies were kept out as well. However, there also were some incomplete values for some of the categories which were insignificant to the conducted analyses.

In the PV data, there were 4,108,250¹² remaining facility entries. 3,894,208 values were missing for the longitude/latitude which does not allow a pinpoint assignment of facilities to their spatial location. Due to this, the facilities were assigned by their postal code, which is only unspecified for 6 facilities (see 4.1.1 for more information). The tilt angle was missing 203,744 datapoints and the orientation angle was missing 175,643 datapoints. While these are certainly significant gaps, they should not influence the result of the generation profile modelling and statistics about the capacity per orientation and tilt angle. Compared to the total number of entries, the missing numbers only represent about 5 % of cases. In addition to that, it can be assumed that the values for the larger facilities are more complete than the values for smaller facilities, which further reduces the influence of this unavailability. Only 35 facilities lacked an assignment to a federal state, which still allowed a meaningful regionalisation. The gross capacity as well as the operational status were fully available.

Regarding the wind data, out of the 31,213 remaining facility entries, 857 were missing for the longitude and latitude, 732 for the hub height, and 361 for the rotor diameter. This did not significantly influence the calculations and implied a good data basis for the following analyses. Fortunately, every facility was assigned to a federal state as well as

¹² Please note that in this thesis, the decimal separator is point (".") and the thousand separator is comma (",")

the sea location, which allowed an effective regionalisation. The gross capacity as well as the operational status were also fully available.

In the following, PV systems that started their operation before the year 1985 were excluded due to the fact that this is unrealistic given the historic development of PV in Germany. To guarantee consistency between the data of the two technologies, this limit was adopted for wind turbines as well. However, this would have only affected one facility anyway.

The collective raw data for the facilities uses an encoding for some categories. In order to correctly label the different characteristics of the categories, they had to be decoded in a prior step. Due to an unavailability of this exact decoding, it was assembled manually using the information of exemplary facilities. Those facilities in the raw data were matched to their counterpart in the web version of the MaStR using a unique identification number. With this information, the assignment of the encoded values to their verbal expression was possible because the web version contains the exact labels for each category. An overview of the respective encodings is given in table 7 (see appendix).

After this step, the preparation of the data was complete, and the analyses were conducted. Many of the analyses included the grouping and summing of data from certain categories¹³ and over time in order to create meaningful statistics about the currently installed renewable energy systems. The precise steps that were taken can be comprehended in the code file that is attached to this thesis.¹⁴

3.3 Capacity expansion pathways per federal state

The future capacity expansion pathways were modelled in total as well as for each federal state in Germany. In addition to that, both technologies (PV and wind power) were analysed separately in order to gain a precise overview of the future plant parks. The foundation of the underlying calculation are the statutory expansion targets, according to §4 of the Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (EEG) 2023¹⁵ for PV and onshore wind power targets as well as §1 of the Offshore Wind Energy Act¹⁶ (“Windenergie-auf-See-Gesetz”) for offshore wind power targets. The years lying in between the target years were linearly interpolated. A comparison of the respective expansion targets is given in table 8 (see

¹³ For example orientation angle, location, hub height, assignment to federal state

¹⁴ See DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14808392>

¹⁵ (Bundesamt für Justiz 25.09.2024a)

¹⁶ (Bundesamt für Justiz 25.09.2024b)

appendix). Those expansion targets were multiplied with the current share of capacity per federal state (compared to the total installed capacity in Germany) for PV and onshore wind to determine the future capacity expansion pathway for each federal state. For offshore wind power, the targets were instead multiplied with the share of capacity between North Sea and Baltic Sea. As will be worked out later in this thesis, the capacity shares between the federal states and between their sea location remained comparably stable in recent years, which justifies this way of calculation. While there are certainly various other possibilities to forecast the future capacity per federal state, that take into account individual developments for every region, this approach was chosen due to complexity reasons.

3.4 Future renewable generation

The future renewable generation represents one of the two pillars to calculate the future RL. It was calculated by applying historical capacity factors to the assumed installed capacity in the future.

The methodology to assume the installed capacity per federal state was already worked out in 3.3. The historical capacity factors were calculated by dividing the realised generation of PV, wind onshore and wind offshore by the installed capacity of PV, wind onshore and wind offshore, respectively. This resulted in a timeseries of specific capacity factors for each technology in hourly granularity. Subsequently, these capacity factors were assigned to the corresponding radiation and wind speeds that appeared in the respective timestep. The resulting relation between the radiation/wind speed and the capacity factor was used to create a function, a so-called “power curve”, that describes this relation for any given input values. For the PV case, a linear regression represents this relation most accurately as there was discovered to be a linear connection of radiation and PV capacity factors. For the wind power case, a sigmoid regression was conducted due to the specific characteristics of wind turbines including their approximately s-shaped appearance.¹⁷ The exact explanation and parameters to fit the functions can be viewed in the attached code. The historic generation data was obtained from Fraunhofer ISE Energy Charts.¹⁸ The fitted power curves are shown in the figures 38-40 in the appendix.

¹⁷ For more information on wind power curves see [wind-turbine-models.com](https://www.wind-turbine-models.com)

¹⁸ (Burger 21.10.2024)

To model the future generation, any desired weather year can be chosen. The radiation and wind speed data of those historic weather years are used as the input of the power curves for the respective technologies. As a result, capacity factors for every timestep of the future year were created based on previous weather years. Thereupon, the capacity factors were multiplied by the assumed installed capacity to model the future generation per technology at a given time. Out of those generation values, the sum was calculated and summarised in a joint timeseries for the key years 2030, 2040, and 2050.

Since the main goal of this thesis is to research possible accuracy gains in the modelling of future RLs, this calculation of the generation was conducted with three different scenarios. As mentioned before, the first scenario “DE_Base_20xx” uses average wind and radiation data of whole Germany to forecast the capacity factors and in turn the future generation. The second scenario “BL_Base_20xx” takes into account regionalised weather data (federal state specific) to estimate the capacity factors per timestep and technology. It can be expected that this result is more accurate due to the fact that there is a higher spatial granularity which considers the different weather characteristics that exist between the federal states. The expected effect of this is that the projected generation increases. This is due to the fact that the consideration of regionalised weather conditions incorporates regional particularities in the modelling of the generation. Generally, there are more favourable conditions for PV electricity generation in the south of Germany and more favourable conditions for wind electricity generation in the north of Germany. As most of the PV capacity is located in the south and as most of the wind energy capacity is located in the north, this leads to an overall higher generation compared to the case of using average weather conditions of whole Germany. Finally, the third scenario “BL_Tech_20xx” additionally includes assumptions on the future technology development of wind energy systems and PV systems. Those assumptions are further specified in the following two subchapters.

3.5 Changes in the future PV generation profile

The precise generation profile of PV systems has a decisive influence on their electricity generation at a certain time. There were different steps taken for the modelling of this generation profile. At first, the current generation profile was obtained. This was done by grouping the data with respect to the orientation and tilt angle as well as the respective gross capacity per facility. The resulting table will be further analysed in 4.1.1 and represents the foundation of the further analysis.

To link these shares to the actual generation that results from them, PVGIS was used.¹⁹ PVGIS is a tool that displays PV generation profiles for any given location in Europe based on various specifications. The generation is modelled based on the input location, the underlying solar radiation database and considered weather years, as well as the specified characteristics of the PV system. In addition to the orientation angle (“azimuth”) and tilt angle (“slope”), the PV technology, peak power, as well as the system loss of the facility can be chosen. Moreover, it is possible to set the mounting type, which allows to model tracked facilities.

Regarding the present analysis, the geometric centre of gravity of Germany was chosen as the location. As no averaged radiation data for Germany can be picked, this was selected as it represents roughly the average solar radiation in Germany. While this certainly poses as an inaccuracy of the model, it should not alter the result significantly because of two reasons. On the one hand, there is a linear relation between solar radiation and PV electricity generation. On the other hand, the result to be achieved is merely a comparison of different generation profiles which is independent from the chosen location. This was validated by a recalculation of the profiles using different locations in the north and south. As this delivered no significantly different results, the chosen location was maintained for the modelling. To implement the weather data, the solar radiation database “PVGIS-SARAH3” was used, as it best represents the analysed area and is the default solar radiation database for this area.²⁰ All available weather years from 2005 to 2023 were included in the consideration. This guarantees a broad data foundation that is less susceptible to weather effects of single years. For the orientation and tilt angle, all possible combinations were chosen that analogously are selectable in the MaStR. As PVGIS does not allow choosing facilities that only rotate along their horizontal axis, this possibility could not be considered. However, as will be shown later, those facilities are only represented by 0.16 % of all existing facilities anyway, which justifies their exclusion. This still leaves 51 out of the 60 possible combinations for the analysis that represent 99.84 % of all facilities. As the MaStR does not deliver exact values for the orientation and tilt angles of the registered facilities, an averaged assumption had to be made. The assumptions for each characteristic of the two categories can be seen in table 9 (see appendix). To generate PV generation profiles, specifications of the PV system had to be entered. Crystalline silicon was used as the PV technology, as it represents the technology with the highest share of global production with 97 %.²¹ In order to compare the different generation profiles to each other at a later point and calculate their differences, the installed peak PV power was set to

¹⁹ (EU Science Hub 23.10.2024)

²⁰ (EU Science Hub 30.09.2024)

²¹ (Fraunhofer ISE 2024)

1 kilowatt peak (kWp). For the east-west oriented systems, the values of the east and west oriented systems were respectively used by 50 % (or 0,5 kWp) and summed up to create a joint generation profile. The system loss was left at its standard value of 14 %.

After downloading the files, they were read into Python and were further processed. The dates of the 29th of February were excluded to ensure consistency with the other years that are not leap years. As the resulting data frames contained the generation profiles of 19 years, the values were averaged on an hourly and yearly basis in a first step. The averaged hourly profiles of different orientation and tilt angles are depicted in figure 2. What is striking is that there are various possible courses of the electricity generation by a 1 kWp PV system.

Figure 2: Average daily PV generation profile based on orientation and tilt angle

Source: own illustration based on own analysis²²

To generate the historic generation profile, the individual generation profiles were multiplied with their respective historic share. Thereupon, the future shares had to be assumed to analogously create the future generation profiles. As will be shown later, the development of east-west oriented PV systems showed a significant increase in recent years whereas south oriented systems grew less strong. On this basis, the growth rate of the last five years (from 2018 to 2023) was used to extrapolate the development of

²² Unless stated otherwise, the source of every diagram in this thesis is an own illustration based on an own analysis

the expansion of the various orientation and tilt angle combinations. In the next step, the sum of the resulting capacities were normalised to fit the yearly expansion targets. Due to this, some capacity values were decreasing again in time. As this is assumed to be unrealistic until 2040, a minimum growth rate of 1 % was introduced and the values were again normalised to the expansion targets. With this calculation, the capacities until 2040 were modelled. Finally, the development from 2040 to 2050 was modelled. Despite there being no further expansion targets after 2040 except from the preservation of the capacity, it was assumed that the composition of orientation and tilt angle changes further. This is due to the fact that older facilities will reach their end of lifetime and new facilities need to replace those systems. Analogous to this, the capacity of systems with orientation and tilt angles that are older should be decreased whereas the capacity of systems with orientation and tilt angles that are newer should be increased. As the lifespan of PV systems was assumed to be roughly 40 years, the facilities that had a high share in 2000 were decreased by 5 % per year while the facilities with a low share in 2000 were increased by 5 % per year. Following this, the values were again normalised to correspond to the target value for 2040.

The resulting extrapolated PV system capacities until 2050 are displayed in figure 3. Similar to the calculation of the historic generation profiles, the shares of different orientation and tilt angle combinations, measured by their capacity were multiplied with the respective generation profile to generate a time series of the future generation profile. As both the historic profiles as well as the future profiles were calculated, the difference between the profiles was calculated in a final step. To achieve this, the profiles of 2030, 2040, and 2050 were divided by the historic profile. The resulting time series shows the relation of the future generation profiles in the three key years compared to the historic generation profile. For the purpose of the analyses, this time series can simply be applied to the future generation data to factor in the effect of changing orientation and tilt angle shares.

To account for the different characteristics of the federal states, the respective use type shares were included in the analysis. The including of the various use type shares allowed the calculation of weighted ground roughness factors. The ground roughness represents the unevenness of the ground surface which affects the friction on the air flow. Therefore, it has a deciding influence on the development of wind speeds in greater heights. Typical values for the ground roughness, that were also chosen in the present analyses, are: $z_0 = 2.0$ m for forest, $z_0 = 0.5$ m for town, $z_0 = 0.05$ m for field, and $z_0 = 0.0002$ m for water.²³ In the following, information on the use type shares per federal state were taken from the Regional database of Germany to weight those values for each federal state respectively.²⁴ An analysis of the current hub height showed that its average value today is about 100 m. Therefore, 100 m was set as the reference height for the calculation. The target height for the years 2030, 2040, and 2050 were determined by conducting an analysis about the expected future hub height, following a logarithmic trend. A detailed explanation of this analysis is given in chapter 4.1.2. In the following, these values were assumed to be the average hub heights in the considered key years: 147.5 m for 2030, 162.5 m for 2040, and 175 m for 2050. Finally, the respective scaling factors per federal state resulted from the logarithmic wind profile equation and were applied to the original wind speed data in the following.

While this approach enables a simple scaling of wind speeds, it should be noted that it oversimplifies the complex influence factors of the increasing height. Therefore, other approaches might turn out to be more suitable. However, this was not considered in the present analysis due to reasons of simplicity.

3.7 Electricity consumption forecasts

The data on the future electricity consumption (load) is a crucial part of the calculation of the RL. The data was obtained from the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) and for Gas (ENTSO-G). ENTSO-E creates a so-called ten year net development plan (TYNDP) that investigates the future electricity system in Europe. As a result of the model calculations within the TYNDP, detailed timeseries of the future electricity profile have been created. These timeseries were published as files that were used in the present analysis. Although the most recent version of the TYNDP is from 2024, it is lacking the detailed look at the hourly demand

²³ (Global Wind Atlas 25.11.2024)

²⁴ (Statistische Ämter des Bundes und der Länder 2024)

profiles. For this reason, the data from the TYNDP 2022 was used. In order to guarantee a consistency with the most recent developments and assumptions, the total sums for the electricity demand were obtained from the 2024 TYNDP and the hourly profile from the 2022 TYNDP was scaled up with these values. This allows to have an hourly timeseries that still has a high relevance due to the consideration of the most recent modelling insights. For the resulting demand profile, both scenarios “Distributed Energy” and “Global Ambition” were averaged. Similarly, the profile scaling factors were also averaged by including both scenarios.²⁵

3.8 Material/data sources

In order to provide an overview of the used data as well as a brief evaluation of the data quality, the main data sources are listed here:

Facility data

- Source: MaStR²⁶
- Usage: 1. To calculate the daily capacity expansion per technology that is used to estimate the future generation + 2. To perform a detailed analysis of the characteristics of those systems
- Data quality: It can be assumed that the data quality is very precise and high because there are data points on the facility level. Furthermore, there can be imposed penalties and the loss of the EEG feed-in tariff, if the facilities are not registered by the operator which poses as a strong incentive to do so.²⁷

²⁵ For more information on the scenarios see <https://2024.entsos-tyndp-scenarios.eu/scenarios-methodology-report/>

²⁶ (Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation, Post und Eisenbahnen 2024)

²⁷ (Verbraucherzentrale.de 23.10.2024)

Generation data

- Source: Fraunhofer Energy Charts²⁸
- Usage: To calculate the historic hourly capacity factors per technology
- Data quality: There is high data quality due to the data being taken directly from the four transmission service operators in Germany, as well as the European Energy Exchange and ENTSO-E.

Electricity consumption data

- Source: ENTSO-E, ENTSO-G^{29,30}
- Usage: To calculate the RL after modelling the future generation
- Data quality: There is high data quality due to robust modelling methods of ENTSO-E and ENTSO-G in large-scale studies that take into account many different influence factors.

PV generation profiles

- Source: PVGIS³¹
- Usage: To model the historic and future generation profiles of PV
- Data quality: There is high data quality due to the use of satellite-based solar radiation measuring.³²

Weather data

- Source: Hersbach et al.³³ – Data on wind speeds and solar radiation can be downloaded from the Copernicus database³⁴
- Usage: To calculate the capacity factors per timestep that are used to estimate the future generation
- Data quality: High data quality due to sound methodology as well as wide recognition and use in the scientific community

²⁸ (Burger 21.10.2024)

²⁹ (ENTSO-G and ENTSO-E 28.09.2021)

³⁰ (ENTSO-E 13.11.2024)

³¹ (EU Science Hub 23.10.2024)

³² For more information see [PVGIS data sources & calculation methods](#)

³³ (Hersbach et al. 2020)

³⁴ [Data source](#)

4 Results

4.1 Current renewable energy systems

4.1.1 PV systems

In order to understand the dynamics and parameters that affect the future generation of renewable energy, it is meaningful to look at key factors and statistics of current renewable energy systems. For this purpose, an analysis of renewable energy systems was made, considering the different characteristics of those systems. In the case of PV, those characteristics were chosen to be the temporal development of capacity of PV systems (for whole Germany and per federal state), the orientation (azimuth angle) and tilt angle of the PV modules, the location of PV modules, the age of the facilities, and the spatial distribution of the facilities. Furthermore, it is also useful to take a detailed look at the combination of orientation and tilt angle and their respective shares among the current PV systems. This will be crucial for the modelling of the future PV generation profile in the considered key years.

Firstly, an overview is given about the general development of PV in Germany. Figure 4 depicts the daily cumulative capacity of PV systems over time. It is visible that the first serious expansion played out between 2009 and 2012 with high growth rates and a so-called “solar boom”, as labelled by the media³⁵. In the following years, this dynamic development noticeably faded (see also figure 5), not least because of changes in the regulatory framework that secured the feed-in tariff for PV systems, the EEG.^{36,37} This also resulted in dramatic consequences for the German solar industry.³⁸ In recent years, the rise of installed PV capacity caught up again, reaching high expansion rates and approximately 80 gigawatt (GW) cumulative capacity by the end of 2023. A potential justification for this development might be the falling prices for PV modules³⁹ as well as increasing efforts to drive forward the Energy transition.

³⁵ (Waldermann 29.06.2009)

³⁶ (Buzer.de 28.08.2024)

³⁷ (ParisTech Review 28.08.2024)

³⁸ (Vorholz 12.04.2012)

³⁹ (Solarserver 2024)

Figure 4: Cumulative PV capacity in Germany

Figure 5: Yearly installed capacity of PV systems

As portrayed in figure 6, Bayern is the federal state that accounts for the highest installed PV capacity of all federal states, followed by Baden-Württemberg and Nordrhein-Westfalen. The reason for this is the high area potential of those states that are among the four biggest federal state by size. Additionally, Bayern and Baden-Württemberg are located in the south of Germany, where the conditions for PV electricity generation are favourable due to the shorter distance to the equator and therefore higher solar radiation.⁴⁰ Contrary to that, federal states that are located in the north, such as

⁴⁰ (Deutscher Wetterdienst 2024)

Niedersachsen, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, and Schleswig-Holstein have a considerably lower share of PV capacity due to worse conditions. The capacity of the so-called “Stadtstaaten” (Berlin, Hamburg, and Bremen) can be neglected in the overall consideration which is because of their small area and higher competition for space than rural areas. In addition, figure 7 shows the cumulative PV capacity divided by federal states.

Figure 6: Capacity of PV systems per federal state

Figure 7: Cumulative capacity of PV systems per federal state

Comparing the temporal development of PV capacity, there are no significant differences between the federal states, at least considering the “Flächenländer”⁴¹ (see figures 41 and 42 in the appendix). In this consideration, 100 % represent the state of the latest data point with the line showing the course that led to this end point. However, there can be observed a time lag of the PV expansion in the “Stadtstaaten”. For example, in 2014 the capacity of most of the “Flächenländer” already reached a share of 40 % of today’s capacity whereas for the “Stadtstaaten” this share was only about 20 % and slightly higher in Bremen with about 30 %. This development goes in line with the delayed expansion of rooftop and plug-in PV systems that represent the main PV location in urban spaces due to lacking availability of space.⁴² This could be a potential explanation for the different speed of the expansion progress.

Finally, the capacity shares per federal state over time were analysed. Figure 8 depicts the relation of the installed capacity in the respective federal state compared to the overall capacity in Germany. In the first years of the PV expansion, the highest share was installed in Nordrhein-Westfalen, but it was replaced in the year 2000 by Bayern that shows the highest share of PV capacity ever since. Interestingly, in the last ten years the respective shares of the federal states stayed approximately the same. This poses as

⁴¹ All federal states except the previously mentioned „Stadtstaaten”

⁴² This development will be shown in detail later in this chapter.

the basis for the assumption that the shares will continue to be on their current level. This insight was used for the forecast of the future PV capacity expansion in chapter 3.3.

Figure 8: Share of installed PV capacity between federal states

Secondly, to gain an insight into the development of the respective facilities, the capacity was analysed over time. Figure 9 portrays this development. Generally, the amount of PV systems installed in a certain period of time (represented by the single dots) increased over time. This is not surprising given the development of PV in Germany that was shown above. The early “PV-boom” between 2010 and 2013 can also be seen as the first facilities surpassed a capacity of 1 megawatt (MW) in this time. In the following years, there seemed to be a capacity limit of 1 MW. This was most likely due to regulatory boundaries of the feed-in tariff that was the crucial criterion for the economic viability of PV systems. In recent years, the shift of the feed-in tariff to a more market based approach, allowed the installation of bigger facilities. Therefore, the range of capacity sizes drastically increased up until a maximum of over 160 MW for a single unit. As some facilities are divided into multiple units, there can be observed even bigger capacity sizes nowadays.⁴³ Simultaneously, there exists a vast and progressively increasing amount of very small facilities. This can be observed by the colour of the markers that represent the number of facilities that have a similar capacity. This dynamic development is especially driven by the expansion of PV systems on rooftops as well as Plug-in PV systems which will be shown by the analysis of the location of PV systems in a later step.

⁴³ (Neubert 03.07.2024)

Figure 9: Capacity of single PV systems over time

Moreover, the large number of small facilities is also expressed by the violin plot that is depicted in figure 10. Similar to a boxplot, it shows the distribution of the data. In addition to that, it gives a more detailed picture of the exact distribution of the values. However, it has to be noted that the highest 5 % of capacity sizes were excluded to ensure the readability of the graph. While this not only shows that 95 % of the currently installed PV systems have a maximum capacity of about 36 kilowatts (kW), it also clearly shows the mentioned concentration on extremely small values.

Figure 10: Violin plot of distribution of PV system capacities

Thirdly, it was analysed how the different orientation and tilt angles of PV modules are distributed among the existing facilities. In figure 11, it is depicted how much capacity is

provided by facilities with different orientations. It can be seen that nowadays the predominant share of PV systems are south-oriented. This is most likely due to the fact that the highest total yield can be achieved with south-oriented facilities in Germany, resulting from the best alignment to the sun.⁴⁴ Another insight can be drawn from the share of east-west-oriented modules that is similar to the share of south-west-/ and south-east-oriented ones. The implications of those facilities to the electricity generation and RL will be discussed at a later point in this thesis in more detail. Tracked facilities that guarantee a perfect alignment at all times show no great relevance which might be due to the high capital expenses on this particular technology.

Figure 11: Capacity of PV systems per orientation

Regarding the temporal development of different orientation angles, figures 43 and 44 (see appendix) depict an overview of the normalised capacity from 2006 to 2024. In these graphs, it can be seen that the capacity of south-oriented PV systems reached 50 % of its current capacity already in 2015, whereas for east-west-orientated systems there was not even 20 % of the current capacity installed. The development of east-west-oriented systems only caught up in the previous years. This insight was used to justify the assumption that east-west oriented PV systems will be expanded more quickly than other orientation angles in the future. Solely east-/ or west-oriented modules seem to follow this trend, although in a more moderate manner. Similar to south-oriented systems,

⁴⁴ (Wirth 2024, 40)

tracked facilities also reached strong points of saturation long before 2024 with only small, stepwise increasements throughout the years.

Complementing the important characteristic of the orientation angle, the tilt angle is the second parameter to describe the features of PV systems. Figure 12 shows that there is a strong concentration on PV modules that are tilted with an angle of below 20° and 20° to 40°. This might be justified by the correlation of south-oriented modules and moderately tilted modules that, in combination, have high yield potentials.⁴⁵ The distribution of tilt angles is also limited by the structural characteristics of the area that should be covered by PV modules which could lead to some options being discarded, for example in roof areas. While there are some modules that have a higher tilt angle of 40° to 60°, extreme tilt angles of above 60° and even 90° can be neglected overall. Similar to the orientation angle, tracked facilities play no decisive role for the tilt angle as well despite enabling a perfect alignment to the sun at all times.

Figure 12: Capacity of PV systems per tilt angle

Regarding the temporal development, the expansion of modules with a tilt angle below 20° was more dynamic in the last years than different tilt angles (see figures 45 and 46 in the appendix). While there was just about 30 % of today's capacity in this category installed ten years ago, facade-integrated and tracked modules already fulfilled 60 % of today's capacity. This correlates with the steep increase of east-west-oriented systems

⁴⁵ (Wirth 2024)

since they are often set up with low tilt angles. Another reason for this development might also be the sharp rise in rooftop PV systems that could be seen in the last ten years (see next paragraph). The capacity expansion of facilities with a tilt angle of 20 to >60° is relatively uniform and follows the trend of the general PV expansion in Germany.

While the separate analysis of the orientation and tilt angle delivered a general impression of the composition of PV modules in Germany, it is more insightful to consider the combination of both parameters. For this reason, a summary of the combined results is given in table 5 with the higher values being highlighted in darker colour. As stated before, the combination of south-oriented and moderately tilted PV modules brings the highest total yield. This results in the highest share of modules being installed in this category with above 50 % in total. It is apparent that there seems to be a concentration of high shares around the predominant, “optimal” composition, due to the highest total achievable yield (see 2.1). Moreover, east-west PV systems represent over 10 % of the total capacity with most modules being tilted only below 20°. As introduced in the theoretical part of this thesis, this combination is chosen with the aim of distributing the generation by the PV systems more evenly throughout the day. This effect will be shown and critically discussed in chapter 4.5, where its implications for the calculation of the RL are displayed. To add on that, it is apparent that north-oriented modules are greatly underrepresented due to their low yield (see chapter 2.1). Finally, tracked modules also show a low share which might be due to high costs for the tracking technology. Out of all tracked modules, two axis tracked modules⁴⁶ have the highest share.

Table 5: Capacity of combined orientation and tilt angle of PV modules in %

	North	North-East	East	South-East	South	South-West	West	North-West	Tracked	East-West
Facade-integrated	0%	0%	0.01%	0.04%	0.16%	0.07%	0.02%	0%	0%	0.02%
>60°	0%	0%	0.01%	0.03%	0.10%	0.05%	0.02%	0%	0%	0.04%
40°-60°	0.02%	0.06%	0.50%	1.29%	4.39%	1.78%	0.69%	0.05%	0%	0.60%
20°-40°	0.18%	0.21%	1.39%	4.53%	31.10%	6.29%	1.95%	0.20%	0.04%	2.42%
<20°	0.62%	0.43%	2.05%	3.87%	20.05%	4.61%	2.25%	0.32%	0.03%	7.15%
Tracked	0%	0%	0%	0.01%	0.09%	0.02%	0.01%	0%	0.18%	0.03%

Source: own illustration based on data from MaStR⁴⁷

⁴⁶ Orientation angle and tilt angle are both optimally aligned at all times

⁴⁷ (Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation, Post und Eisenbahnen 2024)

An important decision in the setup of PV modules is the location where the modules should be installed. The MaStR distinguishes different locations, namely structures (on the one hand “roof, building, facade” and on the other hand “other” that are not closer specified), open spaces, plug-in solar systems (“balcony PV”), water bodies, and large parking lots. An overview of the capacity that is amounted by the different locations is given in figure 13. Interestingly, the predominant installation locations are structures, such as roofs, buildings, and facades. Open spaces account for less than 50 % of the capacity of structures, despite their supposedly bigger facility size. This suggests that there is a very strong decentralisation of the electricity generation because of PV modules that results from a large number of small facilities rather than a small number of large open space PV parks. Regardless of the extensive media reporting on plug-in solar systems in the last year, those facilities play no dominant role regarding the overall capacity, compared to other locations. However, the effect of making the energy transition tangible for individuals and their contribution to the understanding of the required transformation should not be underestimated. Water bodies and large parking lots show even less capacity size, which is most likely explainable by their limited area potentials and increased competing land use. A calculation of the capacity per utilisable area that could be used in the respective category would deliver further insights but is not the scope of this analysis.

Figure 13: Capacity of PV systems per location

Comparing the temporal development of the capacity expansion per location, it is striking that there are two very distinct developments for structures of any kind and open spaces

compared to plug-in solar systems, water bodies, and large parking lots (see figures 47 and 48 in the appendix). The rise in capacity of the latter only began in the recent years, although the development has been very dynamic since then. While this is also partly due to the low general capacity of those alternative locations that enables those high growth rates, it also shows the upward-facing trend of PV modules being installed on the balcony, on the water, and on large parking lots. Especially for plug-in solar systems, there has been a huge expansion in the number of installed facilities in the last months. This is partly due to the recent “Energy Crisis” and the wish to participate personally in the Energy transition, for example to produce own electricity and lower the expenses for electricity from the grid.⁴⁸ It can be expected that this sharp increase will continue because there have been some regulatory changes that aimed at easing the installation of plug-in PV.⁴⁹ Furthermore, there have been significant and persistent cost reductions of the price of PV modules since the beginning of 2023.⁵⁰ Contrary to those “novel” installation locations of PV, the installation on structures of any kind and open spaces follows the general capacity expansion of PV with just little deviations to one another. In summary, the analysis of PV systems per location delivered some meaningful insights but is not needed for the later analysis of the RL. This is the case because the characteristics of PV systems that are needed for the modelling of the electricity generation are already covered by the capacity as well as the orientation and tilt angle.

Connected to the development of PV capacity in Germany, in figure 49 (see appendix) the age of current PV systems is displayed. The graph reflects the yearly installed capacity by arranging the installed PV systems by their age. It can be seen that many PV systems are five years old at the most, which means that the installed capacity steadily increased in the last years. However, there is also a spike in facilities being already twelve years old. This is due to the strong capacity expansion in the years 2010-2013, that was mentioned before. This age structure might have consequences on the efficiency of electricity generation from PV systems but will not be considered in the modelling of the future generation due to complexity reasons.

Finally, the spatial distribution of PV systems in Germany was analysed (see figure 14). Because there is no assignment of coordinates to the facilities in the data, the coordinates were assigned through the postal code and their geographic centre.⁵¹ The resulting map shows the concentration of PV systems in the south of Germany as well as in Nordrhein-Westfalen, that was worked out before. Nevertheless, the area with the maximum of installed capacity is located in Sachsen-Anhalt. This could be due to the

⁴⁸ (Tagesschau 03.06.2024)

⁴⁹ (Presse- und Informationsamt der Bundesregierung 2024a)

⁵⁰ (Solarserver 2024)

⁵¹ (Konrad 2019)

assignment of multiple postal codes to this area which might not represent the result that would occur if the facilities were assigned to their precise location.

Figure 14: Spatial distribution of PV capacity in Germany

4.1.2 Wind power

Similar to the preceding analysis of PV systems, a more detailed look was also taken at the characteristics of wind power. The considered characteristics were the temporal development of capacity of PV systems (for whole Germany and per federal state), the hub height, the age of the systems as well as the spatial distribution of the turbines. Likewise, the current capacity shares per federal state were analysed as the basis for their forecast, similar to the case for PV systems. It was also considered how the hub height changes over time and which implications this has on the future generation.

At first, the general development of wind turbine capacity in Germany was examined. In figure 15, the daily cumulative capacity of wind turbines over time is displayed. Looking at the yearly capacity expansion in figure 16, the development of wind power in Germany shows a steady expansion from 1990 until 2002 where it reached its first peak. Following a phase of weak expansion, the dynamic caught up again in 2013 with high growth rates and a second peak in the year 2017. Shortly after, the expansion broke in and in 2020 there was only as much capacity expansion as could be observed ten years earlier. Since 2021, the growth is recovering. Similar to the cost reduction of PV modules, the costs of wind power technology also decreased in the previous years which is a crucial reason for this expansion.⁵²

Figure 15: Cumulative capacity of wind power

⁵² (Roser 2024)

Figure 16: Yearly installed capacity of wind power

The often mentioned contrast of renewable electricity generation between the north and south of Germany describes the prevalence of different technologies in the respective regions. While the south of Germany has good conditions for PV systems, the north profits from better conditions for wind energy generation because of higher wind speeds⁵³. This relation also can be seen in the visualisation of the installed capacity per federal state (see figure 17). In this case, the northern federal states, mainly Niedersachsen and Schleswig-Holstein perform much better than the ones in the south. Despite their large size and high capacity shares in PV energy generation, Bayern and Baden-Württemberg combined have less installed wind capacity than for example Nordrhein-Westfalen. Yet again, the so-called “Stadtstaaten” have nearly no installed wind power capacity due to the fact that there is a very limited area availability for wind energy in those densely populated areas. Another reason is the so called wind shear that leads to turbulences over uneven areas close to the ground.⁵⁴ Therefore, wind turbines would have to be built in large heights over the buildings which most likely led to both safety and acceptance issues.

⁵³ (Deutscher Wetterdienst 2009)

⁵⁴ (EnBW 2023)

Figure 17: Capacity of wind power per federal state

The cumulative capacity per federal state which adds up to the total capacity of wind power in Germany is portrayed in figure 18. In addition to the electricity generation by onshore facilities of the respective federal states, a significant share is supplied by offshore facilities. The installed capacity of offshore facilities is larger than the capacity of 13 out of the 16 federal states in Germany.

Figure 18: Cumulative capacity of wind power per federal state

Especially in the previous ten years, the expansion of offshore turbines has been very dynamic. This can also be seen in the figures 50 and 51 (see appendix) that show the temporal development of the capacity per federal state. The expansion of offshore wind power set in significantly later than the expansion of onshore wind power. This could be traced back to the reason that the offshore turbines needed to be developed at first and experience was required regarding the installation and operation of wind power on sea before there could be a large-scale expansion of capacity. Another reason is the cost depression which needed to be achieved at first. This made the expansion possible at all. Cases of a more uniform development can be observed in Sachsen and Sachsen-Anhalt. In these states the growth rate declined which is a contrast to the progressive expansion of wind power in general. Furthermore, the strong rise in capacity between 2014 and 2017 that can be observed in other federal states did not take place in Sachsen and Sachsen-Anhalt. According to the BWE Landesverband Sachsen, this is due to a failure of the state government in Sachsen that did not create suitable conditions to identify areas that should be used for wind energy.⁵⁵

In figure 19, the capacity shares per federal state are displayed. It is striking that since the beginning of the wind energy expansion in Germany, Niedersachsen supplies the

⁵⁵ (Bundesverband WindEnergie e.V. - Landesverband Sachsen 2021)

highest share of installed wind capacity compared to all other federal states. However, the share noticeably dropped from 40 % in 1995 to about 20 % in 2024 as other federal states caught up with the expansion of wind energy. Brandenburg and Sachsen-Anhalt showed a strong development of capacity between 2004 and 2012 before their share decreased in the following. In recent years, the share of offshore wind strongly increased, as worked out before already. Apart from this, the share of capacity remained relatively stable in the previous years. This undermines the assumption that the future capacity shares will not deviate from the current state by a large extent.

Figure 19: Share of installed wind power capacity between federal states

Figure 20 takes a more detailed look at the share of offshore wind power capacity between the North sea and the Baltic sea. While the first registered offshore facility started its operation in 2009 in the North Sea, there are also offshore facilities in the Baltic Sea since 2011. In the following, the share of facilities in the North Sea increased again until 2015 with over 95 %. After this, the share of facilities in the Baltic Sea recovered to a share of approximately 15 % in 2019. From 2019 on, the respective shares stayed at a constant level of 85 % for the North Sea and 15 % for the Baltic Sea. Once again, this development is taken as the assumption for the constant development of wind power in line with the worked out shares.

Figure 20: Share of installed offshore wind power capacity between North Sea and Baltic Sea

The plant park of wind power has a different composition than the plant park of PV systems due to much fewer but often more powerful facilities (see figure 21). This can already be seen by the fact that the overall capacity of wind power and PV in Germany is roughly on the same level while there are over 4,000,000 PV systems installed and only about 30,000 wind turbines. However, there is also a much higher scattering of capacity sizes for PV systems. This is because the PV systems are usually summarised in whole parks whereas the wind turbines are listed as single units. What is striking is the increasing dispersion of capacities throughout the years. This is reasoned by the ongoing technology development of wind power and the existence of small facilities at the same time. The capacity of the facilities with the highest density follow the increasing trend, unlike to the case of PV where the highest density could be observed only for smaller facilities. Furthermore, characteristic to wind power turbines, there appear characteristic straight lines for different capacity sizes. This is most likely due to the construction of specific types of wind turbines that have a certain capacity. Especially for small facilities or facilities with about 2 MW of capacity, this is clearly depicted in the graph.

Figure 21: Capacity of wind turbines over time

The distribution of the wind turbine capacities is further portrayed by a violin plot (see figure 22). To ensure consistency with the PV data and in order to be able to compare the two technologies, the highest 5 % percentile is capped again. It can be seen that 95 % of all wind turbines have a capacity of about 5.2 MW at the maximum. This is a sharp contrast to the PV systems where this was only 36 kW. Moreover, the values are not concentrated that extremely on small values because only a small skewness of the distribution is visible.

Figure 22: Violin plot of distribution of wind turbine capacities

One of the most important characteristics of wind turbines is the hub height that, combined with the location of the wind turbine, determines the yield of electricity that is generated. This is ascribable to the different wind speeds at certain heights. In order to take this relation into account and to detect the future height of wind turbines, the hub height of existing facilities was considered in detail. Figure 23 shows the development of the hub height of wind turbines over time.

Figure 23: Hub height of wind turbines over time

Figure 24 expands this consideration with a logarithmic trendline. Each dot represents the hub height of one single wind turbine that is indexed with its respective start-up date. For the vast majority of facilities, the hub height steadily increased due to advancements in wind power technology.⁵⁶ This made the construction of larger towers possible that in turn can harvest higher wind speeds. Interestingly, there seems to be an additional, small cluster of wind turbines with hub heights of 25 m at maximum that show no increase over time. Those facilities might be small wind turbines that are partially built on private spaces and therefore cannot be built higher due to technical or legal constraints, such as distance and height requirements or approval reasons. For example, a small wind turbine for decentralised power supply is not allowed to be higher than 50 m in total (hub height plus rotor radius).⁵⁷ The increase in those turbines that were explicitly constructed as small facilities only started in the year 2009. Contrary to the case for PV systems, there is no accumulation of extreme values but rather an accumulation along the trend line. The strong expansion phases in 2001-2007 as well as in 2014-2018 can be seen

⁵⁶ (Bundesverband WindEnergie e.V. 2024)

⁵⁷ (Solarserver 03.01.2022)

accordingly. In this timeframe, the highest concentration of wind turbines changed from a height of 100 m to almost 150 m. This is depicted by the coloured markings that represent the Point density. In general, the development of wind turbines is seemingly following a logarithmic trend. Therefore, a logarithmic trend line, based on the empirical data, was created in order to create a forecast of the future hub height of wind turbines. The trend line predicts a medium hub height of ~147.5 m in 2030, ~162.5 m in 2040 and ~175 m in 2050.

Figure 24: Hub height of wind turbines over time including logarithmic trend line

Although the rotor diameter is a crucial characteristic for determining the yield of wind turbines, it was not used for this purpose in the estimation of the electricity generation. This is because of the fact that the rotor diameter alone is not necessarily suitable to explain the electricity generation whereas the hub height allows an estimation of the present wind speed. In the following, this wind speed can be used as the argument of the power curve to determine the generation. Another reason for the omission of the rotor diameter is its strong correlation with the hub height that would result in no further insights. Nevertheless, the development of the rotor diameter is shown in figure 52 (see appendix). Analogous to the hub height, it steadily increased, even in a seemingly linear manner. While the first wind turbines only reached a rotor diameter of 30 m, this quickly increased until a state of up to 200 m in 2024. The densest concentration of values also followed an upward facing trend. Identically to the hub height, the rotor diameter also shows a concentration of smaller values that are static over time. Most certainly, those data points belong together and describe the small wind turbines that were discussed before.

The capacity of different ages of wind turbines mirrors the development of capacity over time (see figure 53 in the appendix). Compared to the age structure of PV systems, the age of wind turbines is more evenly distributed. This is mainly due to two differences in the expansion process of the technologies. On the one hand, the large-scale expansion of PV systems set in approximately 5 years later than the expansion of wind turbines. On the other hand, the expansion path of PV shows more obvious expansion phases, whereas the expansion path of wind power is also more evenly distributed. Nevertheless, there is a large number of wind turbines aged between 5 and 10 years due to a strong development between 2013 and 2018. Similar to the case of PV systems, this age structure might have consequences on the efficiency of electricity generation from wind turbines. Identically, this will not be considered in the modelling of the future generation due to complexity reasons. Another effect that plays a role in this context is the replacement of old turbines with new turbines that have a higher capacity, the so-called Repowering. Due to the lacking possibility to extract this information from the data, this effect cannot be considered and poses as an inaccuracy of the model.

The spatial distribution of wind turbines is visualised in figure 25. The methodology to create the map is the same as for the PV systems. However, in this case a more precise assignment was possible because the data contains information on the longitude and latitude of the locations of wind turbines. Contrary to the map for PV systems, the wind turbines are concentrated in the north and north-west of Germany. As mentioned before, this is due to the fact that there exist higher wind speeds in the northern federal states and especially in offshore regions of the North Sea and Baltic Sea. There is a noticeable gradient from north to south that is depicted by the fading of the darker colours. The highest capacity is installed in an offshore region of the North Sea. Additionally, there are many facilities located on the west coast of Schleswig-Holstein, most likely due to excellent wind conditions.

Figure 25: Spatial distribution of wind energy capacity in Germany

4.2 Capacity expansion pathways per federal state

An overview of the forecasted capacity expansion per federal state for each technology is listed in the tables 10-12 (see appendix). A graphical depiction of the tables can be found in the figures 54-56 (see appendix). Regarding the different technologies, there are ambitious expansion targets that require the involvement of every federal state. This results in a strong increase in renewable electricity generation capacity per federal state in the future.

Following the chosen methodology, Bayern, Baden-Württemberg, Nordrhein-Westfalen, and Niedersachsen will have the highest installed PV capacities of all federal states in 2050. In 2040, the total installed capacity will reach its peak of 400 GW, in line with the

statutory expansion target. Bayern alone will have a share of over one quarter of the total PV capacity, which is reasonable because of the high area potential and favourable conditions. There will not necessarily be a further rise in capacity between 2040 and 2050 because there is no additional expansion target after 2040 apart from the conservation of the capacity in 2040.

Differently than for the case of PV, the highest wind power capacities in 2050 will be installed in Niedersachsen, Brandenburg, Schleswig-Holstein, Nordrhein-Westfalen, and Sachsen-Anhalt. In total, a peak of 160 GW will be reached in 2040, according to the statutory expansion targets. Moreover, there will also be a significant expansion of offshore wind power with 70 GW in total. This total capacity is distributed among the North and Baltic Sea while the significantly larger proportion will be installed in the North Sea. This is due to its larger area potential as well as the presence of higher wind speeds. Unlike to PV and onshore wind power, the peak in capacity for offshore wind power will only be reached by 2045, according to the statutory expansion target.

4.3 Future renewable generation

The projected future generation is a result of the modelling methods that were introduced in chapter 3.4. The resulting generation timeseries differ both over the years as well as between the scenarios.

Generally, the generation increases over the years, as ever more capacity is installed, and more renewable electricity can be generated as a consequence. However, the influence of the different scenarios on the generation is not that one-sided. Although the modelling of the capacity factors in scenario "BL_Base_20xx" on average increases the generation, there also exist times of lower generation compared to scenario "DE_Base_20xx". On the one hand, the locations of favourable conditions for PV and wind electricity generation match the locations of the highest installed capacities which leads to a higher generation if this is considered in the data. On the other hand, there are some timesteps where there are unfavourable conditions in the locations with high installed capacity which leads to a higher estimated generation with aggregated input (weather) data. However, this does not take into account the actual situation and should therefore be viewed as an inaccuracy.

The complexity of these relationships is further increasing in the scenario "BL_Tech_20xx". Compared to the previous scenario, it includes assumptions on the

future PV generation profile and wind turbine hub height which both have implications on the projected future generation. Considering the future generation profile, there will be a stretching of the generation profile in morning and evening hours with more generation in these times. Conversely, there will be a compression of the generation profile in midday hours, leading to a lower generation with this scenario approach. In sum, there is a diminishing effect on the total yearly generation, as will be shown in the following chapter. On the contrary, the effect of the increasing hub height is one-sided in the model. This is due to increasing wind speeds as a result of the hub height increase, that always lead to higher generation values in the introduced model (see chapter 3.6 for a detailed explanation of the wind speed modelling).

A detailed comparison of the generation scenarios “DE_Base_20xx” and “BL_Base_20xx” can be seen in figure 26. This analysis was conducted to examine the difference between the aggregated and the federal state specific generation modelling more deeply. The analysis was conducted over all available weather years (1960-2023) and all considered infrastructure years (2030, 2040, and 2050). It calculates the relative difference between the generation timeseries of the aggregated and the federal state specific modelling and compares it by providing key statistical figures.

Figure 26: Comparison of aggregated and federal state specific generation

It is striking that the minimum and maximum difference of the two generation timeseries in a single timestep only differ over the weather years and not over the infrastructure years. This implies that they are mainly dependent on the weather year which is plausible given the estimation of the capacity factors that takes the weather year as their respective input. However, a notable difference can be observed between the range of the maximal positive and negative differences. While the maximal negative difference lies between -0.20 and -0.45, the maximal positive difference is larger with a range of 0.6 to 1.4. This means that for each scenario comparison, there is a timestep where the

federal state specific modelling leads to a generation that is 20-45 % lower than in the aggregated modelling. On the contrary, there is also a timestep where the federal state specific modelled generation is 60-140 % higher than the generation of the aggregated modelling. This indicates that the cases where the generation of the federal state specific modelling is higher than the generation of the aggregated modelling have a larger maximal expression than in the opposite case. Moreover, the range of the maximal positive difference is larger than the range of the maximal negative difference over the weather years.

Regarding the mean of the relative difference, there are both alternations between the weather years as well as between the infrastructure years. The mean lies between 0.07 and 0.12 for all scenarios over the different weather years. This means that on average the projected generation of the federal state specific modelling approach is 7-12 % higher than the generation with the aggregated modelling approach. The reasons for that were mentioned in the beginning of this chapter.

4.4 Changes in the future PV generation profile

The future electricity generation profile of PV was modelled as it represents a further influence factor on the RL. Depending on the specified orientation and tilt angle, an analysis was conducted that calculated the alternation of this profile in the future. This calculation was based on the assumption that there will be different shares of the combinations of orientation and tilt angle for the respective facilities until 2050 (for further information see chapter 3.5). The average generation profiles for different key years can be viewed in figure 27. The fundamental effect of the displacement of south-oriented PV systems by east-west oriented systems is confirmed by this consideration of averaged generation values on an hourly basis. This effect consists of a stretching of the generation in early and in late hours of the day as well as a compression of generation in midday hours. In sum, this leads to a decrease in the total generation because the high position of the sun around the mid of the day cannot be utilised effectively by the east-west oriented plants. For this exemplary case, this leads to a reduction of 2.3 % in 2030, a reduction of 6.4 % in 2040, and a reduction of 9.2 % in 2050 compared to the historic generation of 2023. This reduction is usually accepted because of the higher generation at the beginning and end of the day that is more valuable because there is often low renewable generation to cover the load in these times. As there often exists a

sufficient generation in midday hours, a small loss in generation does not endanger the renewable coverage of the load.

Figure 27: Average daily PV generation profile for different key years

To examine the resulting consequences on the generation more precisely, figure 28 portrays a more detailed picture by considering single days of the year. The hours of the year that correspond to the 21st of March, the 21st of June, the 23rd of September, and the 21st of December were chosen to be analysed. This is due to the fact that on these days the sun is in zenith at the equator and the northern and southern tropic which means that the expected effect can be seen more clearly. On the 21st of June it can be seen that there is a higher projected generation at the beginning and end of day in the future, while the midday hours show less generation. This goes in line with the average daily profiles that are depicted in the previous graph. On the 21st of March and the 23rd of September, the effect on the generation in the morning and evening hours is not that strong and turns over more quickly in favour of the historical generation. On the 21st of December, there is even less generation at all times, which delivers no advantage at all. This is due to the very low position of the sun in winter, leading to a better performance of the stronger tilted south oriented modules. Especially in winter times, where there is a higher electricity consumption than in the summer, this might lead to a further increase in the RL.

Figure 28: Average normalised PV generation on certain days of the year

The final comparison of the profiles is depicted in figure 29. It was conducted by calculating the relative difference in generation of the considered key years compared to the historical reference of 2023. The respective generation profiles are normalised to a capacity of 1 kWp. It is clearly visible that there is an increasing variance of the differences between the profiles until 2050. This is a result of the mentioned effect of east-west oriented PV systems on the generation profile. The median is decreasing which means that there are increasingly more hours of the year where the generation is lower than in the historical case. However, at the same time there are also increasing values for the upper limit of the boxplot which means that there are more hours where the future generation clearly exceeds the historical generation. This is explained by an increase in generation in morning and evening hours up until a factor of 2.1 in 2050. Nevertheless, this extreme stretching only occurs in very few hours of the year. The corresponding compression in the midday hours reaches a maximum value of 0.6 which is slightly lower than the maximal stretching.

Figure 29: Distribution of difference in generation between key years

4.5 Changes in the future wind speed on hub height level

The assumptions of the future hub height that were made in chapter 3.6 lead to higher wind speeds overall and in consequence to a higher generation from wind turbines. As the shares of the use types per federal state are different, there are also different roughness lengths which result in a different scaling of the existing wind speeds. The application of this scaling to the historic data leads to the projected wind speeds in the future. The exact scaling factor for each federal state and year depends on the target height for this year as well as the use type shares per federal state. For the offshore wind speeds, there exist the lowest scaling factors as the roughness length is the lowest for water. The highest scaling factors occur in Hessen, Hamburg, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Niedersachsen, and Nordrhein-Westfalen. The lowest values for federal states occur in Baden-Württemberg, Brandenburg, Bayern, Berlin, and Schleswig-Holstein. The scaling factors range between 103-108 % for 2030, between 104-110 % for 2040, and between 104-112 % for 2050. The resulting upscaled wind speeds are used as an input in the scenario that takes into account the technology development assumptions.

4.6 Future residual load

The future RL was calculated by offsetting the projected future generation with the respective electricity consumption profiles. In sum, this delivers nine scenarios of how the RL is projected to develop in the future. In the following, these scenarios will be examined more precisely.

In a first step, the different scenarios will be compared with respect to their estimated RL in the considered key years. For this purpose, the absolute difference of the scenario “BL_Base_20xx” / “BL_Tech_20xx” and the scenario “DE_Base_20xx” was calculated and examined by key statistical numbers. A summary of the calculated values can be seen in table 6. The relative difference is not shown due to its extremely high values that do not accurately represent the difference between the timeseries. To gain an insight into the order of magnitude of the relative difference, it is more meaningful to look at the comparison of the generation timeseries. In general, the RL in the scenario “DE_Base_2050” is 6.04 GW lower per timestep than in the scenario “BL_Base_2050” and even 10.31 GW lower per timestep than in the scenario “BL_Tech_2050”. This is intuitive given the different generation modelling methods in the scenarios that were already mentioned before. However, the absolute difference between the timeseries is subject to some fluctuations throughout the year, as its standard deviation is 7.42 GW respectively 10.95 GW. The maximal negative difference between the different scenarios is always bigger than the maximal positive difference between the different scenarios for every year. This means that the highest maximal difference in absolute terms between the timeseries occurs when the RL of the scenarios “BL_Base_20xx” / “BL_Tech_20xx” is lower than the RL of the scenario “DE_Base_20xx”. This undermines the observation that the negative RL increases in the refined scenarios.

Table 6: Comparison of RL timeseries for different scenarios

Values in GW	Year	BL_Base – DE_Base	BL_Tech – DE_Base
Mean of difference	2030	-4,28	-7,59
	2040	-6,03	-10,27
	2050	-6,04	-10,31
Standard deviation of difference	2030	5,27	6,03
	2040	7,45	9,69
	2050	7,42	10,95
Maximal positive difference	2030	20,10	15,33
	2040	27,95	32,85
	2050	27,95	41,73
Maximal negative difference	2030	-26,28	-27,94
	2040	-39,21	-41,11
	2050	-39,20	-46,78

Source: own illustration based on own calculations

Figure 30 depicts an overview of the RL across the nine scenarios. It shows the RL in GW for each timestep in the respective year, visualised in separate boxplots. It is striking that there is a clear difference between the considered key years. Both the maximal positive and maximal negative RL increases over the years. Especially the maximal negative RL shows a strong rise from about -60 GW in 2030 up to -150 GW in 2050. This is due to a higher generation from renewable sources, following the massive expansion of PV and wind capacity in the future that is assumed by the model. In summary, the spread of the RL values increases which can also be seen by the increasing spread of the quantiles. Over all scenarios, the median always lies above the mean, that is marked by a yellow dot. This means that the distribution is skewed with more values of a higher RL and just few values that show extreme negative values.

Figure 30: Distribution of RL between scenarios and key years – boxplot

This can also be observed in the corresponding violin plot (see figure 31) that allows a more detailed look on the exact distribution of the values. The mean also expresses an interesting insight, being below zero for nearly all scenarios in 2040 and 2050. This expresses that the total renewable generation by PV and wind over the whole year would be sufficient to cover the total electricity load in these years. While this is certainly interesting to observe, it does not mean that this can be guaranteed in every single timestep. This would only be possible if there additionally was a massive expansion of

electrical storages and if the electricity grid could distribute this electricity without any bottlenecks. The small differences between the years 2040 and 2050 can be explained because the PV and wind onshore expansion are projected to reach their targets already in 2040. Although the wind offshore expansion will reach its target in 2045, this does not alter the resulting generation by a big extent. Apart from only little deviations in the electricity load profile, there are some alternations because of the further increasing hub height of wind turbines as well as an additional change of the PV generation profile.

Figure 31: Distribution of RL between scenarios and key years – violin plot

The increasing number of negative RL events is also shown in figure 32. On the y-axis, the hours of the year are shown. While there are considerably more positive RL hours in 2030, this development turns around in the years 2040 and 2050. In the technology development scenarios “BL_Tech_2040” and “BL_Tech_2050”, the number of negative RL events even exceeds the number of positive RL events.

Figure 32: Positive and negative RL events between scenarios and key years

This consideration is further examined by figure 33, that depicts the sum of the respective RL events, divided into their positive and negative expressions. The sum of the negative RL is further increasing over the key years and exceeds the sum of the positive RL in nearly all scenarios for 2040 and 2050. Once again, this shows that the total renewable supply from PV and wind would theoretically be sufficient to cover the total demand in the future, ignoring the temporal mismatch of generation and supply.

Figure 33: Sum of positive and negative RL between scenarios and key years

Furthermore, the figures that portray the composition of RL events and the sum of the RL were extended by the specific hours of the day that these events occur in. The results

of this consideration can be seen in figures 34 and 35. Looking at figure 34, the dynamic is strongly characterised by the daily course of the PV electricity generation. This can be seen by the large number of negative RL events in midday hours where the generation from PV is high. The period between 19:00 and 22:00 is the period with the highest number of positive RL events. This is due to the low feed-in of PV and a high electricity demand at the same time. Analogously, these reasons also lead to many positive RL events in the first hours of the day, but the effect is weaker. Over the years, the number of negative RL events increases. Nevertheless, the typical daily course with high RL in the morning and evening and low RL in the midday hours can still be observed.

Figure 34: Positive and negative RL events between scenarios and key years per hours of the day

Figure 35 again shows the sum of the RL, but for different times of the day. The positive RL follows the daily course that could already be seen in the number of RL events. However, while the distribution throughout the day stayed approximately the same, there are alternations in the total sum between the years and between the scenarios.

Furthermore, the sum of negative RL drastically increases, almost entirely in the midday hours. Yet again, this is due to the vast feed-in of PV. Comparing the scenarios “BL_Base_20xx” and “BL_Tech_20xx”, it can be seen that there exists a mitigating effect on the RL for the scenarios “BL_Tech_20xx” in morning and evening hours. This is due to a higher generation in these times due to the adjusted PV profile as well as the higher wind speeds that were taken into account. This leads to lower positive RL as well as higher negative RL in the morning and evening but has a contrary implication on the RL in midday hours. While the effect on the positive RL is not that strong, there is clearly less negative RL at noon. Generally, this trade-off is accepted because the lower positive RL in high-demand / low-supply times is valued more than the loss of negative RL in low-demand / high-supply times. However, it has to be noted that this result is only the outcome of the modelling process which should give no closing recommendations, for example on the composition of the future PV plant park.

Figure 35: Sum of positive and negative RL between scenarios and key years per hours of the day

While the results presented in the previous paragraph show a detailed daily course of the RL, the values of the respective hours of the day are averaged over the whole year. Therefore, a comparison of the RL for every (hourly) timestep of the year between three key scenarios is depicted in figure 36. The diagram shows a small bar for every hour and day of the year, beginning with the 1st of January at the top up until the 31st of December at the bottom. The colours indicate the RL that is present in the respective timestep with a scale ranging from dark colours (high values) over light colours (low values) until white (zero). For the scenario “DE_Base_2030”, the dark red values are dominant which means that there are many periods with very high positive RLs. Considering the daily course, these high values occur especially in the morning and evening hours. Apart from that, a clearly seasonal variation is visible as there are lower positive RLs in the summer months and even frequent periods of negative RLs in the midday hours in summer. The seasonal variation is strongly characterised by the PV feed-in. Moreover, throughout the year, but especially in the winter months, there are repeatedly whole days of zero or even negative RL. These times are characterised by a high feed-in of wind power on windy days. Taking a look on the observation for the scenario “DE_Base_2050”, there are similarities but also noticeable differences. The daily and seasonal patterns, that could be observed for 2030, are clearly recognisable. However, the higher renewable generation overall leads to lower positive RLs and stronger negative RLs. Especially in the summer months as well as in spring and autumn there are more periods with higher negative RLs than in 2030. Yet again, this is due to the high PV generation in summer times. Furthermore, the days that are influenced by a high feed-in of wind energy occur more often and in stronger expression. This results in whole days with highly negative RLs, especially in winter times. Finally, to compare the different modelling scenarios, the results of the scenario “BL_Tech_2050” are shown. Compared to the scenario “DE_Base_2050”, the effects of the federal state specific modelling as well as the assumptions on the future technology development are taken into account. Generally, there is a further reduction of the positive RL over the whole year due to the higher estimation of renewable generation in this scenario. The different PV generation profile manifests itself in a stretching of the periods with zero or even negative RL in summer times. Simultaneously, this leads to a small reduction of the highly negative RL in midday hours. Moreover, the frequency of the days in which the demand can be fully covered by wind energy rises further, along with the size of the negative RL in these timesteps. This is due to the generally higher estimated generation of wind energy as well as the increase in the harvestable wind speeds that was assumed in this scenario.

The detailed graphs for every scenario are depicted in figures 57-65 (see appendix).

Figure 36: Comparison of RL for every timestep between three scenarios

To gain further insights into the length of RL events, the scenarios were further evaluated on this objective. Figure 37 portrays a comparison of continuous periods of positive and negative RL between key scenarios. The width of the bars show the length of uninterrupted positive or negative RL periods. The height of the bars corresponds to the sum of positive or negative RL that occurs in this period. Overall, the situation in scenario “DE_Base_2030” is characterised by long periods of positive RL throughout the whole year with only small variations in the summertime. According to the analysis, the longest period of positive RL is 430 hours long and lasts from the 09th of January until the 27th of January. Consequently, the total RL in this period is also maximal with 23,068 gigawatt hours (GWh). Assuming that the last months of the previous year have a similar character than the last months of the considered year, a statement about the RL in winter times can be given. From the mid of November until the end of February, there occurs a period of almost solely positive RL with only few interruptions by negative RL events. In this period, the positive RL amounts to a combined total of over 100,000 GWh, that need to be covered by alternative sources. In the remaining period of the year, the positive and negative RLs are much more fragmented, and they alternate more often. Nevertheless, the periods with positive RL are still clearly longer and show a larger expression. Comparing these findings to the projected situation in 2050 with the scenario “BL_Base_2050”, this will change drastically. Although there is still a recognisable yearly course, it is much less pronounced. The longest periods of positive RL continue to occur in winter but their total extent in GWh is significantly lower and they are more frequently interrupted by periods of negative RL. In summer and significant shares of spring and autumn, the periods of negative RL dominate the overall picture. Furthermore, the sum of the negative RL exceeds the sum of the positive RL. While the composition of the RL in the scenario „BL_Tech_2050” does not change significantly throughout the year, there

are further reductions in the positive RL in winter times and further increases in the negative RL in summer times. Especially in autumn there are longer periods of negative RL.

The detailed graphs for every scenario are depicted in figures 66-74 (see appendix).

Figure 37: Comparison of continuous periods of positive / negative RL between scenarios

5 Discussion

In the following, the main results of this thesis regarding the research questions will be summarized and critically discussed. Moreover, the implications of the results on the future energy system are drawn.

As presented in chapter 4.6, the future RL is subject to vast changes in size, duration and the frequency of positive and negative values. The projected further rise in renewable electricity generation capacity leads to increasingly high negative RL hours of up to -200 GW in 2050, especially in summer times. This is due to the high PV feed-in and the assumed electricity consumption profile that is not flexible enough to allocate the entire electricity demand in supply-heavy times. At the same time, there is a low increase in the positive RL hours that is mainly due to the growing electricity demand in the future and the mismatch of demand and renewable supply in certain times of the year. The maximal positive RL could reach values of about 100 GW. These times refer especially to the morning and evening hours in winter, where the renewable supply cannot satisfy the high demand due to the absence of PV feed-in. Therefore, these hours do not change significantly in the future as there will also be no PV feed-in in those times. Nevertheless, a slowly declining trend across the scenarios can be observed which is due to the higher wind feed-in. The number of negative RL events steadily increases in the future projection because the renewable generation exceeds the demand in more times of the year. Analogous, the sum of the negative RL increases whereas the sum of the positive RL decreases in general. The main times of the negative RLs are the midday hours. As mentioned before, this is due to the massive feed-in of PV. Contrary to that, the main times of the positive RLs occur in the evening hours, especially between 19:00 and 22:00. Again, this is due to high demand and low renewable generation. Finally, the situation of long continuous periods of positive RL, that can be observed now and in the near future, changes in 2040 and 2050. According to the presented model, those periods decrease which is because of higher renewable generation. Especially the higher feed-in of wind energy in the winter plays an important role. Simultaneously, there occur longer periods of negative RL in the future that can be explained by the high PV feed-in in the summer.

Regarding the second research question of the accuracy gains of the model, there are various insights. As the electricity load data is constant over all scenarios, the accuracy gains of modelling the RL refer entirely to the improved modelling of the electricity generation. Firstly, the main accuracy gain is represented by a higher spatial granularity that uses federal state specific capacity and weather data. Secondly, this consideration is expanded by refined assumptions that take into account assumed technology

developments. The higher resolution reflects the actual generation more accurately, which was further described in chapter 4.3. In turn, the estimated future generation in the refined model is higher on average which is due to the consideration that the highest installed capacity can be observed in locations with the most favourable conditions. Thus, only the accurate representation of this fact in the model is what makes this possible in the first place. Although the refined assumptions on technology development are subject to a higher uncertainty, it can be expected that they also lead to a more precise estimation. This is due to the observation that both the PV generation profile, that is based on the orientation and tilt of PV systems, as well as the hub height of wind turbines change in the course of time. Therefore, it would most likely be an inaccuracy to ignore those developments. On the one hand, the projected increase in the hub height leads to a higher generation overall because of higher harvestable wind speeds. On the other hand, the effect of the different PV generation profile is not that one-sided. However, in the introduced scenarios it results in a weakening of both the positive RL (in the morning and evening) and the negative RL (in the midday hours). In summary, the use of higher resolution data improves the accuracy of the model, whereas the refined assumptions on the technologies are more insecure but also contribute to an improvement.

The results of this thesis go in line with findings from other researchers. While there is undoubtedly a consensus about the fact that there will be periods of highly negative RL as well as great challenges to cover the positive RL in the future, the Kopernikus-Project Ariadne estimates different values for the RL in the future. This applies to both the positive and negative values that are projected to reach almost 200 GW and -400 GW at maximum⁵⁸, whereas in this thesis there are different estimations of just 100 GW and -200 GW at maximum. This might be justified by the assumption of higher electricity loads on the one hand and higher renewable generation estimations on the other hand. However, it should also be mentioned that the structure of the future RL is very similar in both calculations, clearly showing the determined daily and seasonal patterns. Although, Kockel et al. also calculated future RL, they cannot be compared to the results of this thesis due to different units and scopes. However, the determined temporal mismatch of supply and demand of renewable electricity is also apparent in their thesis.⁵⁹ Schindler et al. confirm this by once again pointing out the daily and seasonal variation of renewable electricity generation that is mostly influenced by the daily course of the sun, leading to fluctuating PV generation.⁶⁰ Finally, Lehneis et al. did not calculate the future

⁵⁸ (Jürgens et al. 2024)

⁵⁹ (Kockel et al. 2022)

⁶⁰ (Schindler et al. 2022)

RL and therefore their results cannot be compared to this thesis⁶¹. Nevertheless, the outcome of their paper can be used to validate the methodology that was used to model the renewable electricity generation in this thesis. In summary, the present thesis lines up with the fundamental projection of the future RL in Germany, that was already worked out in other research papers. Despite this, there exist insecurities about the order of magnitude of the future RL, as it is influenced by multiple factors and assumptions. Thus, it is challenging to predict this precisely.

The presented results have various possible implications for the future energy system in Germany as well as the field of research. The modelling of the future RL follows the purpose of gaining insights into the initial situation of the future electricity system and is decisive for successfully designing its components. Due to the climate targets of the German federal government, the energy sector has to be decarbonised in order to reach the overall goal of greenhouse gas neutrality until 2045.⁶² This has wide-ranging impacts on the electricity system in Germany. Although the present analysis showed that fluctuating renewable generation plays a crucial role in the future electricity system, it will not be able to cover the demand at all times. Therefore, the future electricity system has to be flexibilised in order to deal with those situations and to guarantee a security of supply at all times.

In consequence, the question arises, how the remaining load, the RL, can be satisfied. Next Kraftwerke GmbH provides a list of various flexibility options that can be used to achieve the temporal harmonisation of electricity generation and demand.⁶³ One possibility is to cover the remaining demand with alternative generation sources. Those sources could be (reserve) power plants or other steerable renewable sources, such as biomass. As the future energy system is aimed to be decarbonised, power plants would need to be fuelled by renewable sources as well. Hydrogen, that is produced in times of negative RL (midday hours where PV generation is high) and utilised in H₂-ready gas power plants⁶⁴ in times of positive RL, could pose as such a source. Moreover, steerable renewable generation can also be provided by bioenergy plants or hydropower plants. The latter can also act as storages, that represent a further crucial flexibility option. Similar to electric batteries, they can be charged in times of high supply / low demand and discharged in times of low supply / high demand. In contrast to those flexibility options, that satisfy the remaining demand in times of low supply, it could also be an option to shift the high demand to times of high renewable supply. These options are called demand side management and describe the adaption of the demand side to the

⁶¹ (Lehneis et al. 2022)

⁶² (Presse- und Informationsamt der Bundesregierung 2024b)

⁶³ (Next Kraftwerke GmbH and Quak 2016)

⁶⁴ For more information on this see [bundesregierung.de](https://www.bundesregierung.de)

generation side instead of the other way round. Furthermore, there also exist other flexibility options, such as optimised energy trading as well as a general expansion of the electricity grids.

While these options are effective ways of dealing with the future RL, there exist problematic issues of both positive and negative RL if the balance of supply and demand cannot be reached at all times. If there is less generation than demand and additional generation cannot be retrieved, the demand has to be lowered. While this is technically possible and there are measures available in the case of this event, this still poses as a threat to the security of supply. This is because some consumers have to lower their demand or cannot consume electricity at all in these timesteps. Therefore, this situation should be avoided by an effective design of the electricity system. Although it is frequently warned about these times of low renewable generation over longer periods, the so-called “Dunkelflaute”, the event of negative RL might also lead to severe consequences in the future. As proposed by Hirth, this is due to a possible overload of the electricity grid following the massive PV feed-in in midday hours. In the worst case scenario, this could lead to the shutdown of single distribution grids with a high feed-in. According to Hirth, the main reason for this situation is the setting of false incentives through the feed-in tariff that disregards the actual value of electricity in certain times of the day. Instead of this valuation, the total amount of generated electricity is remunerated at a flat rate. This incentivises the construction of south-oriented facilities, because they show the highest total yield in Germany.⁶⁵ At the same time, this might lead to the disfavour of east-west oriented systems. As this analysis showed, this is potentially problematic because exactly those east-west oriented facilities could help in stabilising the balance of supply and demand in the grid. Possible solutions for this issue could be a modification of the regulation, an expansion of the grid, as well as the utilisation of flexibility potentials.

Regarding the accuracy gains that can be achieved in modelling the future RL, it can be recommended to use spatially granular data in order to accurately estimate the renewable generation. If this is not possible, the average difference values of the modelled generation between aggregated and more granular data can pose as a correction factor (see 4.3). This correction factor could be applied to the results of the aggregated modelling to take into account the effects of the more granular modelling method and to improve the modelling. However, the use of average values is also unprecise as there are vast differences between the single hours of the year. Moreover, the difference between the methods depend on the considered weather year. A detailed

⁶⁵ (Hirth 2024)

analysis of the plant parks of PV and wind energy might also be useful to accurately represent their technology developments.

The limitations of this research are mainly constituted by further possible accuracy improvements of the RL modelling that are not incorporated into the present analysis. Those limitations refer to several aspects, such as a representation of the electricity grid. This would lead to a more accurate representation of the distribution of the generated electricity. Without this, it is assumed that at all times there exists a sufficient grid capacity that is able to secure this distribution without the need for corrective measures, such as the curtailment of renewable energy systems or Redispatch. However, as this does not represent the actual situation, it can be viewed as a potential to design an even more precise modelling. Due to complexity reasons, this was not taken into account in this thesis. Another reason for this omission is the goal of this analysis that is to show the basic situation of future RL in Germany as well as to deliver basic ideas for an accuracy improvement. Furthermore, the consideration of certain complex relationships could improve the accuracy, for example the effect of wind weakening due to close placement of offshore wind turbines.⁶⁶ However, as this would also massively enhance the complexity and further data would be necessary, it was not included in the underlying model. Moreover, the fitting of the power curves, that are decisive for the generation modelling, can be improved by a federal state specific fitting. In the current model, the fitting is carried out with aggregated data. While this is not methodologically false, the modelling may be enhanced by using more granular data. Finally, more insights might be delivered by a broader scope of the analysis, including interconnections to other countries and their respective plant parks. Again, this immensely increases the complexity and data requirements of the model and is therefore not considered.

Further research could aim at implementing those accuracy improvements with the conduction of a broader based study. However, this would require more resources and data than in this thesis. Nevertheless, the insights of this thesis could be helpful for this purpose, as the underlying model can be built on and further improved. Apart from the potential improvements of the model itself, more research could be aimed at examining the possibilities to deal with the resulting problems. As presented before, the design and ramp-up of flexibility options represent one of these key challenges in the future. While this thesis conveys a picture of the future RL and its challenges, the precise cost-efficient design of its solutions are to be determined in a subsequent consideration.

In summary, the results of this thesis help to get a basic impression of the future RL and its respective problems in Germany. As the negative RL will increase in the future and

⁶⁶ (Agora Energiewende et al. 03.03.2020)

the positive RL has to be covered by renewable sources, the associated problems also become more urgent. Therefore, it will be a great challenge to overcome them by designing the future electricity system in an effective and efficient way. Furthermore, it was shown how the modelling can be made more accurate and additional suggestions for this purpose are given.

6 Conclusion

The goal of this thesis was to examine the future RL in Germany as well as possible accuracy gains of its modelling. Those insights were used to derive implications for the future energy system and to portray how the modelling can be improved.

Regarding the first research question, it was shown that the expected expansion of renewable generation capacity leads to increasingly negative RL in the future. In 2050, there will be values of below -200 GW in single hours, according to the model outputs. Those periods occur especially in the midday hours and are more pronounced in the summer months. This is mainly driven by the high PV feed-in that needs to be managed in order to prevent a system overload. On the contrary, also the positive RL constitutes a serious issue, as it appears particularly in the morning and evening hours in the winter. At these times, when usually no significant renewable feed-in can be expected, values of up to 100 GW can be reached. In 2050, the occurrence of positive and negative RL events is likely to level out or negative RL events will even exceed positive RL events. Although the total sum of positive RL will considerably decrease in the future from over 230,000 GWh in the most optimistic scenario in 2030 to about 130,000 GWh in 2050, it still poses as a problematic issue. This is because it has to be covered entirely by renewable sources in order to comply with the ambitious climate targets. On the contrary, the total sum of negative RL increases from -40,000 GWh in 2030 to -230,000 GWh in 2050. Nevertheless, continuous periods of high positive RL occur especially in winter times whereas continuous periods of high negative RL occur especially in summer times. Both developments necessitate the development of flexibility options that either create alternative generation sources or raise the temporal coincidence of generation and consumption. These options will be key enablers of a stable electricity system in the future and are decisive for the realisation of a successful energy transition.

The second research question concerned the accuracy gains that can be achieved by the modelling of the future RL in Germany. While the electricity consumption data might also hold room for improvement, the current thesis focussed on a more accurate generation modelling. It turned out that a big enhancement can be achieved by the use of more granular weather and capacity data. In this way, the projected electricity generation is more fitting to the actual situation. Moreover, the technology development of the PV and wind turbine plant park harbours further potential for improvement. Although the exact development paths are hard to predict, the lacking consideration of them would result in an inaccurate estimation. This is due to a contradiction to the actual development in the case of their omission. While the proposed accuracy gains contribute to a more precise modelling of the future RL, they are difficult to quantify due to a lack of

possibilities for comparison. Furthermore, there are still various more potentials for improvement that would be conceivable.

As there only exist few studies of the future RL in Germany, the results of this thesis help to get an impression of its situation and its respective implications. Nevertheless, the fundamental insights of this thesis go in line with previous findings. Due to the increasing complexity and urgency of the energy transition, this thesis gives valuable insights that support in developing solutions for the presented challenges. The results of this analysis can be taken up by fellow scientists to create continuing analyses or to further improve the model. Apart from that, the associated input/output data and methodology as well as the related code of this analysis can also be used.

Finally, further research could aim at the examination of the implications of the presented results. Apart from possible additional accuracy gains in the modelling of the future RL, this is a crucial aspect as well. While this thesis only touched upon the consequences of the analysis, ongoing considerations are necessary to develop solutions. Ideally, the results of this thesis contribute to designing the future German energy system in a meaningful way.

7 Appendix

Table 7: Overview of encodings in the MaStR

PV + Wind	
PV	
Wind	

Operational status	
31	In planning
35	In operation
37	Temporarily decommissioned
38	Permanently decommissioned

Orientation angle	
695	North
696	North-East
697	East
698	South-East
699	South
700	South-West
701	West
702	North-West
703	Tracked
704	East-West

Location	
852	Open space
853	Structures (roof, building, facade)
2484	Structures (other)
2961	Plug-in solar system
3002	Water bodies
3058	Large parking lot

Federal states	
1400	Brandenburg
1401	Berlin
1402	Baden-Württemberg
1403	Bayern
1404	Bremen
1405	Hessen
1406	Hamburg
1407	Mecklenburg-Vorpommern
1408	Niedersachsen
1409	Nordrhein-Westfalen
1410	Rheinland-Pfalz
1411	Schleswig-Holstein
1412	Saarland
1413	Sachsen
1414	Sachsen-Anhalt
1415	Thüringen
1416	Offshore

Tilt angle	
806	Facade-integrated
807	>60 degrees
808	40-60 degrees
809	20-40 degrees
810	<20 degrees
811	Tracked

Sea location	
639	Baltic Sea
640	North Sea

Source: own illustration based on data from MaStR⁶⁷

⁶⁷ (Bundesnetzagentur für Elektrizität, Gas, Telekommunikation, Post und Eisenbahnen 2024)

Table 8: Statutory expansion targets in GW

(target values are marked bold, other values are linearly interpolated)

Year	PV	Onshore wind	Offshore wind
2024	88	69	11,1
2025	108	76,5	14,3
2026	128	84	17,4
2027	150	91,5	20,6
2028	172	99	23,7
2029	193,5	107	26,9
2030	215	115	30
2031	233,8	123,4	32
2032	252,6	131,8	34
2033	271,4	140,2	36
2034	290,2	148,6	38
2035	309	157	40
2036	327,2	157,6	43
2037	345,4	158,2	46
2038	363,6	158,8	49
2039	381,8	159,4	52
2040	400	160	55
2041	400	160	58
2042	400	160	61
2043	400	160	64
2044	400	160	67
2045	400	160	70
2046	400	160	70
2047	400	160	70
2048	400	160	70
2049	400	160	70
2050	400	160	70

Source: own illustration based on EEG 2023⁶⁸ and Offshore Wind Energy Act⁶⁹

⁶⁸ (Bundesamt für Justiz 25.09.2024a)

⁶⁹ (Bundesamt für Justiz 25.09.2024b)

Figure 38: Linear regression of the solar radiation on the PV capacity factor

Figure 39: Sigmoid Regression of the wind speed on the onshore wind capacity factor

Figure 40: Sigmoid Regression of the wind speed on the offshore wind capacity factor

Table 9: Assumed values for the orientation/tilt angles in the MaStR

Orientation angle	Assumed value	Tilt angle	Assumed value
North	180°	Facade-integrated	90°
North-East	-135°	>60 degrees	70°
East	-90°	40-60 degrees	50°
South-East	-45°	20-40 degrees	30°
South	0°	<20 degrees	10°
South-West	45°	Tracked	-
West	90°		
North-West	135°		
Tracked	-		
East-West	-90°/90°		

Source: own illustration based on own assumptions

Figure 41: Normalised capacity of PV per federal state – separate visualisation

Figure 42: Normalised capacity of PV per federal state – joint visualisation

Figure 43: Normalised capacity of PV per orientation – separate visualisation

Figure 44: Normalised capacity of PV per orientation – joint visualisation

Figure 45: Normalised capacity of PV per tilt angle – separate visualisation

Figure 46: Normalised capacity of PV per tilt angle – joint visualisation

Figure 47: Normalised capacity of PV per location – separate visualisation

Figure 48: Normalised capacity of PV per location – joint visualisation

Figure 49: Capacity of PV per age of facilities

Figure 50: Normalised capacity of wind power per federal state – separate visualisation

Figure 51: Normalised capacity of wind power per federal state – joint visualisation

Figure 52: Rotor diameter of wind turbines over time

Figure 53: Capacity of wind turbines per age of facilities

Table 10: PV capacity expansion forecast per federal state in GW⁷⁰

Year	BB	BE	BW	BY	HB	HE	HH	MV	NI	NW	RP	SH	SL	SN	SH	TH
2024	7,1	0,3	10,9	24,0	0,1	4,0	0,1	4,0	7,6	10,5	4,4	3,2	0,9	3,8	4,4	2,6
2025	8,7	0,4	13,4	29,4	0,1	4,9	0,2	5,0	9,3	12,9	5,4	3,9	1,1	4,6	5,5	3,2
2026	10,3	0,4	15,9	34,9	0,2	5,9	0,2	5,9	11,0	15,3	6,4	4,7	1,3	5,5	6,5	3,8
2027	12,0	0,5	18,7	40,9	0,2	6,9	0,2	6,9	12,9	17,9	7,5	5,5	1,6	6,4	7,6	4,4
2028	13,8	0,6	21,4	46,9	0,2	7,9	0,3	7,9	14,8	20,5	8,6	6,3	1,8	7,3	8,7	5,1
2029	15,5	0,7	24,1	52,7	0,2	8,8	0,3	8,9	16,7	23,1	9,7	7,0	2,0	8,3	9,8	5,7
2030	17,2	0,7	26,7	58,6	0,3	9,8	0,3	9,9	18,5	25,6	10,8	7,8	2,3	9,2	10,9	6,4
2031	18,7	0,8	29,1	63,7	0,3	10,7	0,4	10,8	20,1	27,9	11,7	8,5	2,5	10,0	11,8	6,9
2032	20,2	0,9	31,4	68,8	0,3	11,6	0,4	11,6	21,8	30,1	12,7	9,2	2,7	10,8	12,8	7,5
2033	21,7	0,9	33,8	74,0	0,3	12,4	0,4	12,5	23,4	32,3	13,6	9,9	2,8	11,6	13,7	8,0
2034	23,3	1,0	36,1	79,1	0,3	13,3	0,5	13,4	25,0	34,6	14,5	10,6	3,0	12,4	14,7	8,6
2035	24,8	1,1	38,4	84,2	0,4	14,1	0,5	14,2	26,6	36,8	15,5	11,2	3,2	13,2	15,6	9,1
2036	26,2	1,1	40,7	89,2	0,4	15,0	0,5	15,1	28,2	39,0	16,4	11,9	3,4	14,0	16,5	9,7
2037	27,7	1,2	43,0	94,1	0,4	15,8	0,5	15,9	29,7	41,2	17,3	12,6	3,6	14,7	17,4	10,2
2038	29,1	1,2	45,2	99,1	0,4	16,6	0,6	16,7	31,3	43,3	18,2	13,2	3,8	15,5	18,4	10,7
2039	30,6	1,3	47,5	104,0	0,5	17,5	0,6	17,6	32,9	45,5	19,1	13,9	4,0	16,3	19,3	11,3
2040	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2041	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2042	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2043	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2044	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2045	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2046	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2047	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2048	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2049	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8
2050	32,1	1,4	49,8	109,0	0,5	18,3	0,6	18,4	34,5	47,7	20,0	14,6	4,2	17,1	20,2	11,8

Source: own illustration based on own calculations

⁷⁰ for explanation of federal state codes see <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Laender-Regionen/Regionales/Gemeindeverzeichnis/Glossar/bundeslaender.html>

Table 11: Wind onshore capacity expansion forecast per federal state in GW⁷¹

Year	BB	BE	BW	BY	HB	HE	HH	MV	NI	NW	RP	SH	SL	SN	SH	TH
2024	9,8	0,0	2,0	3,0	0,2	2,9	0,1	4,2	14,1	8,1	4,5	9,6	0,6	1,5	6,0	2,1
2025	10,9	0,0	2,3	3,3	0,3	3,2	0,2	4,7	15,7	9,0	5,0	10,7	0,7	1,7	6,7	2,3
2026	11,9	0,0	2,5	3,6	0,3	3,5	0,2	5,2	17,2	9,9	5,5	11,7	0,8	1,9	7,3	2,5
2027	13,0	0,0	2,7	4,0	0,3	3,8	0,2	5,6	18,7	10,7	6,0	12,8	0,8	2,0	8,0	2,8
2028	14,1	0,0	2,9	4,3	0,3	4,1	0,2	6,1	20,3	11,6	6,5	13,8	0,9	2,2	8,6	3,0
2029	15,2	0,0	3,2	4,6	0,4	4,4	0,2	6,6	21,9	12,6	7,0	14,9	1,0	2,4	9,3	3,2
2030	16,3	0,0	3,4	5,0	0,4	4,8	0,2	7,1	23,5	13,5	7,5	16,1	1,0	2,6	10,0	3,5
2031	17,5	0,0	3,6	5,3	0,4	5,1	0,3	7,6	25,3	14,5	8,1	17,2	1,1	2,8	10,8	3,7
2032	18,7	0,0	3,9	5,7	0,4	5,5	0,3	8,1	27,0	15,5	8,6	18,4	1,2	3,0	11,5	4,0
2033	19,9	0,0	4,1	6,1	0,5	5,8	0,3	8,6	28,7	16,5	9,2	19,6	1,3	3,1	12,2	4,2
2034	21,1	0,0	4,4	6,4	0,5	6,2	0,3	9,1	30,4	17,5	9,7	20,8	1,3	3,3	13,0	4,5
2035	22,3	0,0	4,6	6,8	0,5	6,5	0,3	9,7	32,1	18,4	10,3	21,9	1,4	3,5	13,7	4,7
2036	22,4	0,0	4,6	6,8	0,5	6,6	0,3	9,7	32,3	18,5	10,3	22,0	1,4	3,5	13,8	4,8
2037	22,5	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,6	0,3	9,7	32,4	18,6	10,4	22,1	1,4	3,5	13,8	4,8
2038	22,6	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,6	0,3	9,8	32,5	18,7	10,4	22,2	1,4	3,6	13,9	4,8
2039	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,6	0,3	9,8	32,6	18,7	10,5	22,3	1,4	3,6	13,9	4,8
2040	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2041	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2042	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2043	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2044	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2045	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2046	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2047	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2048	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2049	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8
2050	22,7	0,0	4,7	6,9	0,5	6,7	0,3	9,8	32,7	18,8	10,5	22,4	1,4	3,6	14,0	4,8

Source: own illustration based on own calculations

⁷¹ for explanation of federal state codes see <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Laender-Regionen/Regionales/Gemeindeverzeichnis/Glossar/bundeslaender.html>

Table 12: Wind offshore capacity expansion forecast per federal state in GW⁷²

Year	North Sea	Baltic Sea
2024	9,8	1,7
2025	12,4	2,2
2026	15,0	2,7
2027	17,7	3,1
2028	20,3	3,6
2029	22,9	4,0
2030	25,5	4,5
2031	27,2	4,8
2032	28,9	5,1
2033	30,6	5,4
2034	32,3	5,7
2035	34,0	6,0
2036	36,6	6,5
2037	39,1	6,9
2038	41,7	7,4
2039	44,2	7,8
2040	46,8	8,3
2041	49,3	8,7
2042	51,9	9,2
2043	54,4	9,6
2044	57,0	10,1
2045	59,5	10,5
2046	59,5	10,5
2047	59,5	10,5
2048	59,5	10,5
2049	59,5	10,5
2050	59,5	10,5

Source: own illustration based on own calculations

⁷² for explanation of federal state codes see <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Laender-Regionen/Regionales/Gemeindeverzeichnis/Glossar/bundeslaender.html>

Figure 54: Future cumulative capacity of PV per federal state

Figure 55: Future cumulative capacity of onshore wind power per federal state

Figure 56: Future cumulative capacity of offshore wind power per sea location

Figure 57: RL for every hourly timestep (DE_Base_2030)

Figure 58: RL for every hourly timestep (BL_Base_2030)

Figure 59: RL for every hourly timestep (BL_Tech_2030)

Figure 60: RL for every hourly timestep (DE_Base_2040)

Figure 61: RL for every hourly timestep (BL_Base_2040)

Figure 62: RL for every hourly timestep (BL_Tech_2040)

Figure 63: RL for every hourly timestep (DE_Base_2050)

Figure 64: RL for every hourly timestep (BL_Base_2050)

Figure 65: RL for every hourly timestep (BL_Tech_2050)

Figure 66: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (DE_Base_2030)

Figure 67: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (BL_Base_2030)

Figure 68: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (BL_Tech_2030)

Figure 69: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (DE_Base_2040)

Figure 70: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (BL_Base_2040)

Figure 71: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (BL_Tech_2040)

Figure 72: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (DE_Base_2050)

Figure 73: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (BL_Base_2050)

Figure 74: Periods of continuous positive and negative RL (BL_Tech_2050)

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